

Master's thesis

Little Boxes of Sustainability

Tracing CSRD Reporting Practices in the Norwegian Real Estate Sector

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Abstract

There are many sustainability issues that pose serious harm to people and the environment: rising sea levels, deforestation, and the ongoing exploitation of workers serve as persistent reminders. One growing approach to mitigate these harms is sustainability reporting, where companies are expected to document their impacts and outline measures for addressing them. As part of this shift, the European Union has introduced the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) as a new reporting framework aimed at enhancing legibility and commensurability in how sustainability is measured and disclosed. In this study, I examine what this realignment toward standardization and comparability means in practice.

I draw on qualitative interviews with Chief Sustainability Officers (CSOs) in eleven Norwegian real estate companies, combined with analysis of key regulatory documents. Through this, I trace how the directive is translated into internal practices, assessment methodologies, and ultimately, audit-ready reports. The analysis is grounded in Science and Technology Studies (STS), particularly Actor-Network Theory and valuation studies, to explore how sustainability is rendered legible by translating conflicting valuation processes into the language of financial accounting.

The findings show that the CSRD does not enter organizations as a fixed object, but is translated and negotiated through new routines, technical templates, and concepts. In this process, tensions emerge between local expertise and standardized demands. CSOs must make future risks and opportunities measurable, translating qualitative judgments into quantitative facts. Many experience this as a shift from enacting sustainable solutions to producing abstract reports for distant users.

By tracing this process, the study shows how sustainability information is not merely reported but actively shaped through ongoing sense-making and negotiation. This approach reveals how visions of sustainability are constructed, and at times disconnected, when entangled with the processes of financial accounting.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Term
APP.	Appendix
AR.	Application Requirement
Art	Article
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CSO	Chief Sustainability Officer
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DM.	Double Materiality
DR	Disclosure Requirement
EC	European Commission
EFRAG	European Financial Reporting Advisory Group
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
IG	Implementation Guide
IROs	Impacts, Risks, and Opportunities
Paras	Paragraphs
Rec	Recital
SBM	Strategy and Business Model

Preface

I would like to sincerely thank everyone who has supported me throughout this process. To my family and friends - your encouragement and care have meant more than I can say.

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Thank you! Isabella Thalia Starrfield Oslo, May 2025

Chapter 1

Introduction

What does it mean when a company claims it is ‘sustainable’ or ‘accountable’? These words are everywhere - in investor presentations, company reports, product packaging. For some, they might feel empty or abstract, too vague to be meaningful. For others, they may signal that a company, activity, or product is somehow less harmful *in some way*. Yet, behind these labels lie spreadsheets, metrics, procedures, judgment calls - and laws. Some information is included, and some is not. Some people agree in this process, and some do not. But in any case, someone, somewhere, decides what gets to count as sustainable.

In this study, I examine one particular attempt at standardizing sustainability reporting: the implementation of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), formally known as Directive 2022/2464/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on corporate sustainability reporting (hereafter: Directive 2022/2464/EU). While the CSRD promotes transparency, comparability, and verifiability, this thesis analyzes the underlying work of producing legibility and commensurability in sustainability reporting. To understand what the CSRD sets out to achieve and how its ambitions are translated into situated organizational contexts. I conducted interviews with Chief Sustainability Officers (CSOs) across eleven companies in the Norwegian real estate sector. Drawing on these interviews, alongside key documents in the network of actors surrounding the CSRD. I explore how the issue of sustainability is reshaped in the process, and how companies make sense of, adapt to, and operationalize the directive’s requirements. In doing so, I examine how sustainability practices are shaped, categorized, and made reportable in the process.

The use of measurement and documentation to manage sustainability is not new. From the Greenhouse Gas Protocol, which standardizes how companies record and calculate their greenhouse gas emissions (World Resources Institute & World Business Council for Sustainable Development, 2004), to laws like Norway’s Transparency Act, which requires businesses to gain an overview of and report on human rights and social conditions in their businesses and supply chains (Barne- og familiedepartementet, 2021). These frameworks are designed to make complex issues more visible, and therefore more manageable.

But visibility also invites judgment. These frameworks create ways of assessing how well a

company aligns - or fails to align - with certain sustainability ideals. They allow outsiders to compare, rank, and evaluate. Yet the comparisons aren't always as straightforward as they seem. Different methods of measuring produce different pictures. What counts as good performance in one framework might look very different in another. In this landscape, even *sustainability itself* becomes a matter of interpretation. So what happens when comparison, ranking, and evaluation become central values in sustainability governance? Suddenly, having multiple ways of measuring, picking the frameworks that fit their company or activity, doesn't just create confusion - it becomes a problem. If companies can't be compared, how can we know who's doing well, who's falling short, or where investments should go?

The reason this has become such a pressing issue is simple: without reliable, and comparable information, sustainability data can't be used in a *meaningful way*. This speaks to a broader push toward harmonization (Laurent, 2022) - a growing effort to align how companies measure and report on sustainability, so that information can be compared across firms, sectors, and borders. Without a common ground for comparison, it's hard to make informed decisions - or to act at all. The CSRD builds directly on this premise. The directive document states this lack of transparency and consistency limits the usefulness of sustainability information for everyone who depends on it (Directive 2022/2464/EU, recital 9). These "users" are varied. They include customers deciding where to shop, NGOs choosing partners, regulators determining how to enforce accountability, and investors assessing risk and opportunity. For each of them, information is only useful if it's trustworthy - and if it can be compared across companies, sectors, and countries (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 9).

This is the promise the CSRD was designed to deliver on. It responds to a growing need - not just for *more* sustainability information, or for information that is *standardized* and thus easy to compare (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 44), but also for information that is also *credible* (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 60). The directive introduces requirements for external verification and audit, aiming to legitimize the content of sustainability reports (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 5 ; rec. 13). This framework is situated within the European Green Deal and the Action Plan: Financing Sustainable Growth (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 1 ; rec. 2), the European Commissions' growth strategies for tackling climate change. The aim is to align all major policy areas - including finance, trade and industry - with long-term climate goals, redirect capital to sustainable investments, and promote transparency and long-term thinking in financial markets (Council of the European Union, 2025; European Commission, 2018). Rising global temperatures are seen not only as an environmental threat, but also as a risk to long-term social and economic stability. To confront this, the European Commission has called for a systemic transformation in how sustainability is assessed, valued, and reported. A core part of this strategy is through the *mobilization*, of capital markets: steering financial flows toward sustainable projects. The EU estimates that reaching its climate targets will require an additional €260 billion in investment every year (European Commission, 2019).

At first glance, this may seem entirely rational, that reaching climate targets will require massive investments in clean energy, battery innovation, and new technologies. And for that, financial flows must be redirected. However, a closer look reveals the foundational

assumptions embedded in the CSRD's design. First, it rests on the belief that achieving economic growth and reaching environmental targets can happen simultaneously. Secondly, it assumes that a growing concern about issues like climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource depletion will motivate investors to act in alignment with sustainability goals. Third, it presumes that this motivation can be activated through the production of standardized, audited sustainability information, produced through the same rigorous procedures of financial accounting. Taken together, these assumptions position financial systems not merely as compatible with sustainability, but as essential for driving it forward. Yet, as (Ahola-Launonen & Kurki, 2022) argue, EU policy is being pulled in two conflicting directions - on the one hand, a persistent commitment to economic growth, and on the other, by emerging policies aimed at protecting environmental value. This entanglement of sustainability with institutional logics rooted in economic growth has been critiqued as resting on a conceptually unstable and potentially contradictory foundation.

(Chiapello, 2015, 2020) argue that the rise of financial instruments in environmental regulation often privileges investor-oriented transparency and short-term profitability over substantive ecological outcomes. From this perspective, environmental concerns are reformatted to align with market logic, thereby sidelining more transformative forms of environmental accountability. Extending this perspective, (Engen & Asdal, 2024a) explore how a climate-finance nexus is emerging, not solely through market-driven priorities, but through the interplay between conceptual developments and processes of industry consolidation. They trace how the notion of climate risk is broadened to encompass risks to the financial system itself - risks that arise as a consequence of stricter environmental regulation. These transformations, the authors argue, do not result from a single political decision or overarching strategy, but unfold through the gradual, routine work of building socio-technical systems.

From this perspective, the CSRD is not merely a reporting framework - it is part of a broader regulatory project that has gradually taken shape, building on years of development that have slowly redefined how sustainability comes to be understood, valued, and acted upon. This echoes Power (2015) argument that regulatory systems rarely emerge through grand strategies, but rather through the slow and gradual implementations of templates, routines, and metrics - mechanisms that make some things visible, while obscuring others. As we will see, the CSRD does not dictate specific outcomes. Instead, it reshapes how information is gathered, structured, and deemed legitimate. It is not only an effort to steer capital toward sustainable projects of firms, but also a process of mobilizing financial actors to create these measurement and reporting devices (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec.39 ; EFRAG (n.d.)) - bringing them in to help define what sustainability means, how it should be measured, and which forms of knowledge are allowed to count. What is at stake, then, is not just *what* gets reported - but *how* the very meaning of sustainability is being reconfigured in the process. As sustainability becomes aligned with the forms, procedures, and logic of financial accounting, a tension emerges between the push for formalized, auditable definitions and more situated, context-sensitive understandings.

1.1 From Voluntary Disclosure to Formalized Reporting

The gradual shift in how sustainability is understood and operationalized has not emerged spontaneously - it builds on earlier policy efforts and frameworks. This evolution reflects a broader shift in environmental regulation that predates the CSRD. As early as the 1980s, voluntary environmental auditing mechanisms began to take hold (Power, 1999). This trajectory led to the predecessor of the CSRD; the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), which laid the groundwork by creating a framework for companies to disclose environmental, social, and governance (ESG) matters (Directive 2014/95/EU, 2014). While the NFRD represented a first step of sustainability reporting in the context of the European Union, its voluntary and flexible nature was increasingly viewed as inadequate for producing information that was useful. The CSRD was constructed to address these perceived shortcomings, representing a move toward formalization, standardization, and accountability. Unlike its predecessor, the CSRD mandates that sustainability reports follow detailed standards, are externally audited, and published alongside annual financial statements (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 5 ; rec. 17 ; rec. 21). The CSRD sets out an ambitious and detailed reporting structure that reflects both the breadth of sustainability concerns and a push for formalized, comparable data. ¹ Companies are now expected to report across 12 ESG standards, covering topics such as climate change, resource use, the circular economy, and affected communities, as outlined in Annex I to Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772 supplementing Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards sustainability reporting standards (hereafter: EU 2023/2772). Each standard is further unpacked into detailed sub-topics and sub-sub-topics, reflecting an emphasis on specificity and breadth. These include, for example, climate change mitigation, impacts and dependencies on ecosystem services, and measures against violence and harassment in the workplace (EU 2023/2772, 2023). The inclusion of such wide-ranging topics within a single reporting framework illustrates just how far the CSRD reaches - folding distinct, and at times disconnected, concerns into a single standardized system of disclosure. In practical terms, this translates into approximately 82 detailed disclosure requirements, and potentially more than 10,000 underlying data points (PwC Netherlands, 2023). Altogether, the wide range of topics and the large number of required data points - covering everything from emissions and ecosystem impacts to workplace policies and corporate conduct - show an effort to create a reporting system that is both comprehensive and highly structured.

Although, the wide range of topics and the large number of required data points reflect an effort to build a reporting system that is both comprehensive and highly structured - with the goal of creating more meaningful and actionable sustainability information. The very structure that enables such standardization can also obscure the complexity behind the data. As Espeland and Sauder (2007, p. 72) observe, rankings and other comparative systems, often appear most objective to those furthest removed from the intricacies of their construction. A similar dynamic plays out in sustainability reporting: data must be retrieved from diverse sources, transformed

¹The actors and processes involved in developing the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), such as the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG), will be examined further in Chapter 4.

through software systems and accounting tools, and negotiated across actors from different contexts and with different forms of expertise. What ultimately gets included - or left out - is rarely self-evident.

Another important feature of the CSRD is its use of performance indicators: quantifiable metrics designed to track how well an organization is progressing towards its sustainability goals (Directive 2022/2464/EU, Art. 19a). With around 500 such indicators included in the CSRD (PwC Netherlands, 2023), this shift reflects what Power (1999) describes as a move from direct regulatory enforcement to internalized, managerial forms of control. Responsibility is no longer framed solely through compliance with fixed external targets, such as reducing emissions by a certain percentage. Instead, organizations are expected to develop systems that can monitor, document, and demonstrate their own performance. In this model, what is governed is not only the environmental outcomes, but the structures and procedures that claim to manage them - a form of oversight Power (1999, p. 62) terms *second-order control*. The CSRD thus aligns with a broader "managerial turn", where demonstrating accountability becomes as important as the actions themselves.

What opens up as an interesting entry point to studying the CSRD is precisely the tension between how sustainability issues are framed, the systems developed to measure and manage them, and the negotiations over what ultimately gets included or excluded. These interpretive processes - shaped by tools, judgment, and competing priorities - are likely to become invisible to those who only encounter the final report. It is therefore crucial to examine these processes before they appear settled. This tension - between the promise of structured, comparable reporting and the messy realities of producing it - runs through the CSRD's architecture and forms the core of the analysis in the chapters to come.

1.2 Research Questions and Goals

As the previous sections have aimed to show, sustainability reports are not simply objective depictions of how companies affect the environment. Studying the emergence of increasingly formalized sustainability reporting frameworks, such as the CSRD, reveals more than an institutional effort to promote transparency - it offers insight into how sustainability is being redefined through data practices. These practices do more than reflect sustainability efforts; they shape them. The choice of metrics is never neutral (Nost & Goldstein, 2022), and formalization does not automatically lead to transparency or meaningful oversight (Ghosh & Faxon, 2023). Examining the CSRD provides a unique entry point for studying broader contemporary dynamics: how actors are reconfigured, how collaborations are assembled, and how boundaries are drawn around seemingly abstract concepts such as sustainability. Where earlier forms of sustainability regulation often focused on direct interventions - such as outlawing toxic emissions above a fixed threshold or mandating safety equipment on construction sites ² - contemporary reporting requirements introduce a different mode of

²Examples include the EU REACH Regulation (EC No 1907/2006) (European Parliament and Council, 2006), which restricts harmful chemical substances, and Directive 92/57/EEC (Council of the European Communities, 1992), which sets minimum safety and health requirements for temporary or mobile construction sites

governance: one that targets internal systems, future risk, and potential improvements. While highly practical in implementation, this approach extends the scope of intervention from concrete harms to anticipatory measures (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, Appendix A, Application Requirement 15) and internal performance indicators (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS E1, Disclosure Requirement E1-E3). Today, the "problem" of sustainability is less something we can see directly, and more something that takes shape through complex networks of actors, metrics, and classifications. Understanding how sustainability becomes knowable - and actionable - within these networks is central to this study.

As already discussed, a growing body of literature questions how well the alignments between sustainability, finance, measurement devices, and external verification works in practice (Chiapello, 2015, 2020; Engen & Asdal, 2024a; Ghosh & Faxon, 2023; Loconto, Prudham, & Wolf, 2024; Power, 1999). This study builds on these insights by following how sustainability reporting is practiced and negotiated within the Norwegian real estate sector. Through this case, I aim to get closer to sustainability, transparency, and accountability - not as abstract policy ambitions, but as something enacted in the everyday work of reporting. I argue for the importance of studying sustainability practices where they are actually done - where reports are compiled, indicators are interpreted, and the messy realities behind the numbers unfold. This study offers one entry point into understanding what happens when broad sustainability policy is put to work in everyday organizational setting.

To explore these dynamics, I focus on what I consider a key site where translation, negotiation, and organizational practice converge: the role of Chief Sustainability Officers (CSOs) in the Norwegian real estate sector. I conducted interviews with CSOs from both large and small companies - some operating with dedicated sustainability teams, others managed by a single individual or folded into broader roles. While some of these firms are known for their sustainable building portfolios, others stand out primarily for their financial performance. The CSOs I spoke with represent a diverse range of professional backgrounds: some trained as engineers, others as economists, and many occupy positions that bridge technical and managerial expertise. What connects them is their function as intermediaries - working at the intersection of regulatory requirements, internal priorities, and evolving sustainability frameworks.

In addition to interviews, I analyze key directive documents and one selected implementation guide. These documents are not passive block of text, but active instruments shaped by assumptions, associations, and intended modes of use. By tracing how these texts travel - how they form issues, prescribe tools, and are interpreted - and sometimes contested - I aim to understand what happens when a regulatory ambition like the CSRD moves through diverse organizational and professional settings. What emerges is not a single, coherent form of knowledge, but multiple and sometimes competing ones: efforts to make sustainability legible, to align it with business models, and to satisfy the expectations of auditors and consultants. Through this process, new relationships take shape: between actors, between forms of expertise, and between regulatory ideals and situated practices. This study explores how these relationships are configured - and argues that processes of connection and disconnection

become central mechanisms for understanding this process of sustainability reporting.

As a result of these questions, I have developed the following research questions:

- *How is the CSRD framed as a response to a sustainability problem - and what actors, tools, and processes of valuation are mobilized in bringing it into being?*
- and,
- *How is the CSRD translated into the Norwegian real estate sector, and how does it challenge and reshape existing practices and collaborations?*

1.3 The Thesis Structure

Chapter 2 outlines the theoretical framework of the thesis. I situate the project within Science and Technology Studies (STS), explaining the choice to draw on analytical tools from Valuation Studies and Latourian Actor-Network Theory. I then review literature relevant to my case, to further situate my work. As there were no STS studies focused specifically on the CSRD - and very few on sustainability reporting more broadly - I instead focus on core dynamics within these domains. This includes work on measurement tools used to value nature and on audit cultures, in order to explore how concepts like accountability, measurement, and sustainability are connected and made operational.

Chapter 3 presents the methodological foundation of the thesis. I explain my choice to employ interviews and practice-oriented document analysis to help me answer the research questions, and reflect on the research process more broadly. This includes considerations around case selection, data collection, and my role as a researcher throughout the study.

Chapter 4 is my analysis chapter, structured around three key parts in the implementation of CSRD:

Part 1 explores how the CSRD constructs and defines the issue it seeks to address. Drawing on Asdal and Reinertsen (2022) turn to studying documents as *doing issue modification work*, I show how directive documents not only reshape the sustainability issue but also what actors are mobilized within this network. The chapter begins to surface tensions in how these frameworks are taken up in practice, revealing that valuation is not merely technical but a site of negotiation between professional worlds. In this way, Part 1 maps the problem space and lays the groundwork for the analysis that follows.

Part 2 turns to the organizational settings where the CSRD is enacted in practice. Here, Chief Sustainability Officers (CSOs) play a central role in translating regulatory expectations into internal action - mobilizing departments, building workflows, and coordinating both data and people. Positioned between external demands and internal structures, CSOs continually engage in sense-making while aligning sustainability work with reporting requirements. This part traces how sustainability is transformed through iterative processes of data gathering, stakeholder engagement, and internal negotiation.

Part 3 examines the process of translating sustainability concerns into formalized structures to then be made auditable in the final stages of CSRD implementation. As companies move from gathering inputs to projecting risks and opportunities, sustainability work becomes increasingly anticipatory - requiring actors to translate uncertain futures into standardized formats. This shift brings new challenges for CSOs, who must exercise professional judgment within rigid templates that often obscure the meaning of the data they report.

Chapter 5 concludes the thesis by reflecting on how the practices within CSRD reshapes sustainability practices. I consider what this case reveals about the challenges of making sustainability legible, and bring together my research questions to assess the kind of sustainability processes the CSRD enables and the tensions it produces in practice.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Framework

Before I can begin to trace the network of relations that the CSRD is embedded within, I first need to establish the theoretical ground on which this thesis stands. This chapter lays out the framework that will guide my analysis. To do so, I have decided to divide the chapter into two main parts.

Section 2.1. presents and justifies the broader theoretical approach. I situate this thesis within the field of STS and outline the affordances this perspective offers. Within STS, two strands are particularly central to my work: Actor-Network Theory (ANT) and valuation studies. I will discuss how these perspectives inform my approach and the types of questions they enable me to ask. While in section 2.2, I turn to selected studies relevant to the themes and dynamics present in the CSRD and its implementation. Since the CSRD has yet to be widely studied within STS, I have drawn on adjacent literature that deals with relevant processes and instruments. I argue that these works provide valuable entry points and analytical tools that will help me make sense of the empirical material to come.

2.1 Situating the Study: Approaching Sustainability Through STS

This thesis situates itself inside the field of Science and Technology Studies (STS). To understand the approach I take, it is helpful to briefly trace how the field emerged and what it sets out to do. STS began taking shape in the 1960s and 70s, a period marked by political upheaval and growing skepticism toward institutions of authority. In this context, scholars sought to better understand the relationship between science, technology, and society. Moving away from simplistic binaries and instead examining how these domains co-produce one another (Cozza, 2021). At its core, STS questions taken-for-granted distinctions: science versus politics, subjects versus object, or the social versus the technical. Rather than assuming these as fixed or natural categories, researchers within STS study the processes and work through which boundaries are actively constructed (Asdal, Brenna, & Moser, 2007).

This orientation gave rise to one of the field's earliest and very significant shifts: a methodological move toward ethnographic studies of scientific practice. A foundational example is in the book *Laboratory Life* by Latour and Woolgar (1986, 1979), which approached

the scientific laboratory not as a neutral site of discovery, but as a place where facts are constructed through a network of social, material, and rhetorical practices. Their work showed that scientific authority is not simply a product of empirical rigor, but rather as something assembled through everyday acts and interactions. The perspective of seeing scientific knowledge as situated, constructed and contingent remains central to STS, and it provides a key starting point for the theoretical tools I bring into my own analysis. What follows is a more detailed presentation of the specific STS approaches that guide my thesis: Actor-Network Theory (ANT) and Valuation Studies.

2.1.1 Analyzing the CSRD through Actor-Network Relations

Actor-Network Theory (ANT) emerged in part from the ethnographic turn exemplified by Latour and Woolgar's *Laboratory life*, as discussed above. From its inception, ANT has included several prominent contributors and has since evolved in diverse directions. In this thesis, I focus primarily on the work of Bruno Latour, particularly his 1990 essay *Drawing Things Together*, while also drawing selectively from others in the field of ANT whose concepts I argue are complementary. Building on STS's broader call to examine how realities are made, ANT pushes this further by insisting we map and follow the actors in their interactions. Rather than applying a predefined analytical framework, ANT encourages us to trace how networks of human and non-human actors form, how they interact and mutually shape one another, and how durable structures emerge from these fragile and shifting associations. In this view, stability is never assumed although it can be achieved. Therefore, what matters is not only who the actors are, but what associations they form, what tools they rely on, and how these relationships allow particular versions of reality to hold. What matters is not only *who* the actors are, but *how* their associations—with tools, procedures, documents, and metrics—allow particular versions of reality to take hold. ANT also reconceptualizes *agency*. Rather than being an inherent trait of individuals, agency is seen as a *relational effect* - emerging through associations between heterogeneous elements (Latour, 1990). This enables a "flat" analytical approach to the CSRD, in which human actors, institutions, templates, and concepts are treated symmetrically as part of the network shaping what counts as sustainability.

ANT offers a diverse set of analytical tools, and different studies can draw on different parts of its evolving tradition. In this thesis, the toolbox I find most relevant is the one Bruno Latour presents in his 1990 essay *Drawing Things Together*. That text explores, in Latour's words, "how insignificant people working only with paper and signs become the most powerful of all" (Latour, 1990, p. 60). This provides a particularly fitting entry point for studying the CSRD. As we will see, the CSRD process is, to a remarkable extent, constituted through documents: directive texts, implementation guidelines, spreadsheets, templates, and even emails. The call to action is issued on paper, and the result of that action is yet another paper - the sustainability report. My analytical interest lies precisely in how one collection of papers gives rise to another. *Drawing Things Together* offers a rich collection of analytical tools for tracing how text, symbols, graphs come into being, what actors are brought in to create them, and how does this process, and what it produces, influence what sustainability is. To do this, I open up this ANT toolkit to describe how it enables me to analyze the CSRD as a process of assembling,

translating, and coordinating knowledge through paper and signs.

If we understand a report, document, or directive as something designed to make certain issues visible - and perhaps to shape how others act or think - then we must also investigate the conditions under which it becomes possible. To study the CSRD - and the forms of agency it enacts - it is crucial not to take its existence for granted. Rather than treating it as a fixed or self-evident structure, we must examine how it is set into motion, maintained, and made operational. Here, the concept of mobilization becomes analytically useful. Latour (1990) defines mobilization as the process through which actors, devices, and priorities are gathered and aligned to produce seemingly stable outputs. From this perspective, reporting is not a neutral endpoint but the outcome of extensive backstage work: negotiations over what is included or excluded, how information is formatted and which representations are granted authority. Who or what is mobilized to bring these representations into being? What alliances are formed, and what forms of labor become invisible under the surface of the finalized report? By attending to these questions, we can begin to unpack how the CSRD operates not merely as a set of documents, but as a dynamic and contingent process of assembling knowledge and coordinating action. To further examine how mobilization unfolds in the network of CSRD, I draw on an additional concept from Callon (1984, p. 204): the notion of *obligatory passage points*. This term describes situations where a particular actor or element becomes essential - something that all information or actions must pass through in order to move forward.

If we continue with the image of information flowing through a network, then it must move - from one place, one context, to another. In other words, information must be *displaced* from its original setting. Latour (1990) describes displacement as the movement of knowledge from a context-rich environment into new spaces where it can circulate and be acted upon. The reporting process of the CSRD naturally, then, requires a process of displacement. Where information must be drawn from specific contexts, the contexts the companies operate in, and be transformed in ways that allow them to travel across diverse organizational and institutional landscapes. For such displacement to be meaningful, the information must be rendered legible to those who were not part of its original production. This is where *inscriptions* become central. Latour (1990) argues that the power of scientific - and by extension, organizational - practices lies not in their access to objective truths, but in their ability to produce simplified and portable representations: graphs, tables, checklists, and reports that make complex realities understandable and actionable for those outside of those contexts. These inscriptions transform situated, messy phenomena into forms that can move across settings while retaining a coherent meaning, and as a result, enabling coordination and oversight at a distance. As Latour (1990, p. 34) puts it, this involves a shift from "watching confusing three-dimensional object to inspecting two-dimensional images which have been *made less confusing*." Another key point emerges here: information does not simply flow unchanged through networks. Instead, it is *translated* as it moves. This means that information can be reshaped, re-framed, or redefined during its journey. By employing these analytical tools, I am able to study how locally situated knowledge and sustainability practices within Norwegian real estate companies are displaced, translated, and circulated into other realms. This includes examining how context-specific information is transformed to standardized formats, how it flows through obligatory passage

points, and how it is rendered legible and actionable through inscriptions.

What becomes analytically interesting, then, is not to study whether these visualizations represent an objective truth, but how they work to align actors and make the world "less confusing." Issues like biodiversity loss, CO2 emission, and global warming are undoubtedly real, but they are not always easily seen, measured, or acted upon. To render such issues visible and manageable, they must be translated into legible forms - chart, indicators, reports. This translation process involves condensing complex, context-dependent realities into simplified, transportable representations. Yet this simplification is never neutral. It requires decisions about what to include, what to omit, and which perspectives to prioritize. In making some things visible, other elements - including the compromises, assumptions, and negotiations involved - are obscured. As Latour (1990, p. 60) reminds us, inscriptions are "immensely less than the things from which they are extracted." What appears as a neutral snapshot is in fact the outcome of coordination and alignment. These representations shape not only how sustainability is communicated, but how it is understood and enacted. Sustainability reports, in this view, do not simply describe - they participate in constructing.

This perspective underpins my analysis of the CSRD. By drawing on these conceptual tools, I trace how the actor-networks in the process of constructing sustainability reports as artifacts of translation, constructed through mobilization, displacement, and inscriptions. By attending to how sustainability data is transformed into standardized and portable forms, I am to study how the CSRD acts as a technology of coordination, shaping what counts as sustainability - and for whom.

2.1.2 Valuation Devices and the Construction of Sustainability

While ANT equips me with tools to study how information flows and how actors are mobilized and aligned within networks, I also want to understand why certain configurations are pursued - what makes some translations desirable, and why actors support, contest, or attempt to reshape them. To complement this network-oriented analysis, I turn to valuation studies. Drawing on Muniesa's (2012) reading of John Dewey, I adopt a perspective that shifts the focus from what something is worth to how value is made. Rather than treating value as fixed or as a reflection of pre-existing preferences, valuation studies understand valuation as an active, situated process. Value is not simply discovered; it is constructed - through practices, tools, and judgments that unfold in specific contexts. This perspective allows me to examine how sustainability data does not just circulate, but becomes worth acting on. Valuation is, according to Muniesa, performative: not only attributes value, but helps bring that value into being. As the author goes on to argue, "something does not have the same value before and after it has been valued; value depends on how valuation is done (2012, p. 28)." This creates an entrance for me to analyze how overlapping valuation practices interact - within and across organizations, regulatory frameworks, and reporting processes. Allowing me to explore how particular versions of sustainability gain traction, while others may be sidelined. In this way, valuation studies support my broader aim of understanding the complexities of how sustainability is translated by, and through, the CSRD.

The sites explored by valuation studies are diverse, but the field can be broadly traced to the shift in STS from opening up the laboratory to opening up the economy. Over time, this approach has increasingly brought in the importance of devices - such as accounting instruments or pricing models - in shaping what actions are made possible or constrained (Muniesa, Millo, & Callon, 2007). Rather than treating markets, society, and technology as distinct domains, this literature emphasizes their entanglement in sociotechnical arrangements. This lens is especially useful for analyzing how sustainability reporting unfolds under the CSRD; it enables attention to how specific devices and configurations mediate what is valued within the conception of sustainability, and what is left out. While Muniesa et al. (2007) focus on the role of *market devices* in organizing economic action and constructing market realities, I will use the concept of devices more broadly to study the conception of new sustainability realities. Actors such as traders or sustainability officers do not passively use tools; their reasoning and decisions are shaped through them. Understanding the performative role of such devices allows me to explore how valuation under the CSRD is not just about describing sustainability, but actively producing a version of it.

Especially relevant to this study, is comparative case study *Cents and Sensibility* Fourcade (2011) and the analysis of legal and political responses to major oil spills: the *Exxon Valdez* in the U.S. and the *Amoco Cadiz* and *Erika* in France. Her analysis centers on three interrelated questions: why money is used to value non-market goods such as nature, how these valuations are carried out in practice, and what consequences they produce. As Fourcade (2011, p. 1726) notes, even "in an era of alert environmental consciousness," the worth of nature can come to be understood through economic valuation techniques and processes of commensuration. The calculations and devices used to translate environmental harm into monetary terms are never neutral, but rather contingent on broader contexts, and may be shaped by conflict, negotiation, or coexistence among competing valuation processes. In this way, by studying valuations as active processes, paired with their translation into inscription, gives me tools to study the CSRD as a configured network where procedures, systems, and institutional logics coalesce to make valuation possible.

Given that the CSRD is situated within broader policy frameworks such as the Green Deal and the Action Plan for Financing Sustainable Growth, as outlined in the introduction, the perspectives and analytical tools brought forward here provides a valuable entry point for mapping the associations within this network.

2.2 Sustainability Through Audits, Metrics, Commensuration

I have now presented the key analytical tools that guide this thesis, particularly from ANT and Valuation Studies. This section adds to these by bringing together ideas from different areas of research - like critical policy studies, the sociology of audits and numbers, and studies on finance and sustainability - to explore how sustainability as a site and as a practice comes to be modified. These perspectives complement one another and together build a more comprehensive understanding of the case at hand as it will sensitize me to the mechanisms, structures, and dynamics that shape sustainability reporting under CSRD. Although not all of

these works focus directly on sustainability, they provide valuable concepts and examples that help us understand how sustainability gets shaped through administrative, financial, and legal measurements, and practices.

The core of the CSRD is that the final report will be verified through *auditing*, therefore, drawing on Michael Power's book *The Audit Society* will give important insights into what this means. Auditing here is defined as processes of verification and assurance that aim to produce trust yet simultaneously rely upon it (Power, 1999, pp. 3–4). Power further states that auditing practices increasingly govern modern organizations through standardized tools, performance indicators, and verification mechanisms 1999. In doing so, technological devices - such as checklists and analytic tools - are employed to *perform* objectivity, despite their inherent dependence on professional judgment (Power, 1999, pp. 29–30). Power characterizes auditing as embracing a “vague scientific rationality,” a deliberate ambiguity that obscures its reliance on subjective interpretation to sustain legitimacy (Power, 1999, p. 76). Auditing thus functions less as a transparent verification method and more as an institutionalized performance, creating the appearance of objectivity (Power, 1999, p. 123).

Parallel to this analysis on auditing, is another entry point to studying the verification of seemingly objective information. This can be seen through the increased use in metrics in a process of transforming diverse, qualitative realities into standardized, commensurable forms (Espeland & Stevens, 1998). Metrics do not merely measure reality; they actively configure and govern it by embedding specific values, institutional priorities, and economic logics (Fourcade & Healy, 2016). Metrics such as financial accounting standards (Chiapello, 2016), digital scoring systems (Fourcade & Healy, 2016), and sustainability rankings shape organizational perceptions of value, influencing which types of knowledge and perspectives gain influence (McElwee, 2017; Stephenson, Schoenefeld, & Leeuw, 2019; Winickoff & Mondou, 2017). Crucially, metrics simplify complexity, narrowing space for nuance, and sometimes replacing reflexivity with procedural compliance (Lassiter, Jean Cadigan, Haldeman, Reavely, & Henderson, 2016), or displacing certain values, with others. For example in shifting ecological and ethical concerns to market-oriented, audit-compatible procedures (Fouilleux & Loconto, 2017).

This is not to say that using metrics to guide decisions is a straightforward process, as an increased focus on transparency and data-driven governance through metrics can diminish accountability by introducing ambiguity, opacity, and inconsistencies (Cool, 2019; Fejzic & Usher, 2025; Freidberg, 2020; Nost, 2022). Metrics and standards, therefore, can become arenas for negotiations and reflexive engagement by organizational actors (Cusworth, Brice, Lorimer, & Garnett, 2023; Demortain, 2024; Pelizza & Van Rossem, 2024). Rather than passively accepting these evaluative criteria and measurement devices, organizations can actively shape and challenge them, demonstrating the dynamic and performative nature of metric-based governance (Pollock, D'Adderio, Williams, & Leforestier, 2018).

Several of the mechanisms discussed in the literature above also appear in Laurent's book *European Objects: The Troubled Dreams of Harmonization* (2022) which explores how objects play a central role in the functioning of European regulation. These objects have agency;

they help shape what forms of public participation is possible, sometimes making it easier and sometimes more difficult. To explain this, Laurent introduces the idea of harmonization, which he says is guided by two main goals: disentanglement and objectivity. Disentanglement relates to standardizing the objects, making them more similar, so they can move easily across borders. Additionally, there is an investment in the idea that expertise, such as from scientists, will construct these regulations *objectively*. Harmonization therefore is the aim to increase cohesion between EU member states by creating shared standards for laws and markets, with a reliance on formal expertise. However, the envisioned cohesion created, Laurent argues, often translates into bureaucratic overreach as local issues can consequentially be treated as technical problems, stripped of their social and political meaning. In other words, the promise of neutrality and precision in harmonization often results in rigid systems that make it harder to incorporate local realities.

Taken together, these perspectives provide a rich analytical lens for understanding how sustainability reporting under the CSRD is shaped by verification practices, metrics, and regulatory infrastructures. In doing so, it is important to unpack the assumptions embedded within these measurement and reporting devices, what relationships they have with local complexities, as well as analyzing how they might come to be negotiated.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological approach I have taken in this project, as well as the tools and strategies I have used to generate and analyze data in response to my research questions. I begin by describing the design of the case study and the motivations behind my choice of topic. I then present the primary method used in this study: semi-structured interviews. I discuss the data collection process- from recruitment to transcription. Afterwards I set my sight on the secondary method: practice-oriented document analysis. I discuss how these inform my perspective and method. Because the processes of analysis, interpretation as well as ethical considerations shaped and unfolded continuously alongside data collection, I incorporate steps from the analytical process throughout the chapter, rather than presenting them in a separate section. I do the same with how the NESH guidelines for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and Humanities (2024) have shaped my methodological decisions. This approach aims to reflect the iterative and reflexive nature of the research as it developed over time. I conclude this chapter by reflecting on my role as a researcher.

3.1 Research Design and Case Selection

My path into this topic was far from linear. I had long held a vague interest in the European Union (EU), though my impressions were full of contradictions. On one hand, I saw the EU as a powerful regulatory force, responsible for landmark initiatives like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). On the other hand, I also saw it as slow and overly bureaucratic - a distant apparatus of paper-pushers in Brussels. In other words, my impression was built largely on the fragmented pieces of information I would be exposed to through the news, friends, or other informal settings. The EU felt so vast and abstract that it was difficult to form a coherent picture of it. At the same time, my studies in Science and Technology Studies (STS) were beginning to shape the way I saw the world. STS made me more aware of the invisible processes behind things we often take for granted. I came to realize that even something that seems straightforward - like basing policy on research - is in fact full of negotiations, compromises, and technical constraints. I became increasingly interested in how things that appear impossibly large, or insignificantly mundane, play a role in the messy realities of

governance and organization. Rather than viewing the EU as a distant behemoth, I began to see it as made up of practices, tools, and structures. There is no inherent power in these alone, and no simple, one-way flow of influence. Instead, power is enacted through messy, material, and local processes.

So in beginning the process of writing this thesis, I knew I was interested in a process. A process of something as big as a transnational framework to become locally implemented. I spent months trying to find an example of such a process that I could deep-dive into. I researched carbon markets, data protection regulations, but it wasn't until I began using the carrier social media LinkedIn that I found something that truly interested me. This happened when my LinkedIn feed suddenly became full of companies talking about the new Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). They kept saying how excited they were about the "challenge" it presented. Being a naive student who is not familiar with business language, I thought, "Wow, that's cool - everyone's actually excited about this!" That's when I started getting curious about what CSRD really was. As I began exploring the topic, STS helped me study the CSRD not just as a new rule, but as a whole process of creating and organizing knowledge, values, and practices; but as something with agency, restructuring and reshaping.

The reason I chose to focus specifically on the real estate sector in Norway stems from a research project I participated in on Oslo's Planning and Building Authority (Plan- og bygningsetaten) and their new strategy for high-rise development. Comparing the final strategy document with the public hearing process, I became fascinated by how deeply entangled urban planning is with material, social, and political concerns. Buildings and construction emerged as a meeting point between so many of the aspects that make up society around us, and still, so deeply intertwined with political processes and negotiations. I began to uncover how sustainability, could be highly contested terrain shaped by valuation practices and competing priorities. Questions about what matters - ecologically, economically, or socially - show up in very tangible ways: Should a building use low-carbon materials or maximize floor space? Should it preserve a view, or is it okay if it casts shade on a nearby playground? What might seem like technical decisions often turn out to be about priorities and values. This made me realize that the built environment is full of everyday negotiations over sustainability - and that construction and real estate are great places to study how these negotiations unfold in practice. It also helped me see the CSRD not just as a reporting framework, but as something that tries to organize and make legible these messy, value-laden decisions.

3.1.1 Case Selection and Recruitment Strategy

This thesis uses a qualitative case study design to explore how sustainability reporting practices are unfolding within Norwegian real estate companies in response to the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). A case study approach was chosen because it enabled me to examine an ongoing and dynamic process - one where practices are still being developed, negotiated, and sometimes contested. Following Yin's (2018, p. 33) guidance that case studies are particularly useful for "how" and "why" questions in real-world contexts, this design provided the flexibility needed to capture how different organizations

are experimenting with CSRD implementation in practice.

This project was approved by SIKT (Norway's national center for research data) and adheres to the NESH Guidelines for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and Humanities NESH (2024). Ethical considerations were embedded throughout the research process, from recruitment and consent to data storage, analysis, and representation. The project follows an inductive research design where analysis is shaped by empirical findings rather than predefined hypotheses. This flexible approach is well-aligned with ethical research practice, as it allows for reflexivity and attentiveness to participants' meaning-making and situated experiences (NESH, 2024, p. 7).

Rather than focusing on a single organization, the case centers on the broader process of CSRD preparation and reporting across the Norwegian real estate sector. It is both processual and sectoral in nature (Yin, 2018, p. 66), bounded by geography (Norway) and the time-frame leading up to their first CSRD-aligned reports (2024–2026). By including companies with varying ownership structures - ranging from independent firms to subsidiaries of larger groups - I was able to observe how organizational configurations shape reporting strategies. Including companies at different stages of CSRD readiness also gave insight into how interpretations of the directive vary.

I used strategic sampling as my recruitment approach, based on the principle that qualitative studies benefit from informants who are well-positioned to provide insight into the research questions (Grønmo, 2016, p. 105). My initial goal was to conduct interviews across a few selected organizations but with a diversity of roles - data analysts, financial officers and sustainability professionals - within a few selected companies. However, after reaching out to four companies, each pointed me to their Chief Sustainability Officer (CSO) as they key contact for questions related to CSRD. This recurring redirection revealed the centrality of the CSO role in how sustainability reporting practices are organized and navigated. As a result, the project shifted from an internal focus on data transformation processes, to a broader, case-based inquiry into how the CSRD is being implemented across companies in the same sector. In this sense, the selection of CSOs as informants was not only shaped by recruitment dynamics, but also reflected a growing analytical recognition that this was where the core dynamics of the case were unfolding.

Even with this shift, I maintained an emphasis on variation. The final sample was selected to reflect differences in organizational structure, reporting readiness, environmental positioning, and CSO backgrounds. To identify suitable firms, I followed a four-step sampling strategy:

1. I mapped the sector using publicly available sources (such as dedicated real estate news sites and the yellow pages).
2. I cross-referenced these companies with databases for environmental building certifications - although I do not mention specific certification schemes or frameworks here in order to preserve anonymity - and reviewed publicly available financial statements to ensure variation in both sustainability orientation and revenue levels.
3. I reviewed company websites and reports to identify those already engaged in CSRD-related activities, either by searching for the CSRD by name, or by cornerstone

assessments such as double materiality.

4. As I noted variation in CSOs' academic backgrounds - ranging from engineering and finance to communications and social sciences - I aimed for a blend of disciplinary perspectives in the final sample.

I decided to pair a case study design with interviews and document analysis. This decision was both practical and analytical. While I initially considered ethnography, access to constraints made this unfeasible: most companies were under significant pressure from upcoming reporting deadlines and did not allow onsite observation. Additionally, I wanted to move between the site of meaning-making (the organizations) and the site of requirement-making (the regulatory documents), and interviews combined with document analysis were well suited to this.

This approach enabled me to balance inductive openness with systematic engagement across multiple sources. In practice, I moved iteratively between interviews, CSRD documents, and relevant academic literature. While this project was exploratory, (Yin, 2018, p. 38) I entered the field with a theoretically informed interest in expertise, valuation logics, and data infrastructures - concepts primarily drawn from STS. These theoretical orientations functioned not as fixed frameworks but as navigational tools (Kvale, 2007, p. 54), helping to sensitize my analysis to recurring themes. Although this study does not aim for statistical generalization, it seeks to contribute to analytical generalization by linking case-specific insights to broader discussions about sustainability reporting, organizational auditing, and how regulation is shaped through everyday practice.

While this thesis examines both EU-level regulatory documents and company-level practices, it does not treat them as two isolated spheres. Instead, it investigates the interface where these domains meet. The combination of interviews and document analysis reflects this orientation: rather than drawing a dichotomy between policy and practice, I follow how sustainability reporting is shaped through the ongoing interactions between actors. This approach aligns with STS sensibilities, which emphasize relational processes over fixed categories, and highlight how practices like reporting take shape through entangled interactions across multiple sites.

3.2 Interviews

This study relies on semi-structured interviews to explore how sustainability reporting practices are operationalized in the Norwegian real estate and construction sector under the CSRD framework. The interview process was guided by Kvale's (2007) seven-stage model for qualitative interviewing, emphasizing open inquiry, reflexive engagement, and iterative learning. The purpose of this thesis is to explore how sustainability reporting practices unfold in the construction and real estate sector in light of the EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). The project investigates how organizations collect, classify, and validate sustainability data, and how different forms of expertise - such as sustainability professionals, financial controllers, and auditors - negotiate what counts as credible or relevant information.

My goals was to conduct approximately ten interviews. To manage outreach and logistics, I developed a local spreadsheet containing anonymized information on candidate firms, participant roles, and contact status. Entries were coded with general descriptors (e.g., "Company A - Informant A - Contacted") and stored in Obsidian, a local note-taking application, on an encrypted, password-protected device with no cloud sync or third-party plugin access. The file was deleted after the data collection phase. This tracking system helped ensure diversity across company types and professional perspectives. Eleven companies ultimately participated. In most cases, the Chief Sustainability Officer (CSO) or the individual responsible for CSRD reporting served as the interviewee, allowing me to focus on how sustainability expertise is mobilized internally and how external requirements are translated into organizational practice. One company without a dedicated sustainability team assigned the responsibility of reporting to a HR manager, who then became the informant.

3.2.1 Overview of Informants

The interviews were conducted with sustainability professionals from Norwegian real estate and urban development companies. All informants held primary responsibility for CSRD-related reporting. Figure 3.1 provides an overview of the informants’ educational backgrounds and the length of each interview. For anonymity, participants are referred to using numerical codes (CSO1, CSO2, etc.), throughout the thesis.

Table 3.1: Overview of interview informants

Informant	Professional background	Interview length
CSO1	Economics	48 minutes
CSO2	Civil Engineering	30 minutes
CSO3	Civil Engineering	32 minutes
CSO4	Finance	30 minutes
CSO5	Political Science	60 minutes
CSO6	Civil Engineering	33 minutes
CSO7	Public Relations	30 minutes
CSO8	HR ¹	33 minutes
CSO9	Environmental Systems	31 minutes
CSO10	Construction engineering	30 minutes
CSO11	Engineer, energy efficiency in buildings	35 minutes

3.2.2 The Interview Guide

Given the exploratory nature of the project, the interviews were designed to allow the informants to lead the conversation (Kvale, 2007, p. 53). While I had prepared a thematic guide, my questions were formulated in a descriptive and open-ended manner (Kvale, 2007, p. 73), with the aim of capturing how CSRD-related reporting practices unfold in everyday work. My goal in developing interview questions was to be as concrete and specific as possible - an approach by what Asdal & Reinertsen (2022, p. 171) call practice-oriented interviews. I aimed to

¹At the time of the interview, the company did not have a dedicated sustainability team. The informant had been assigned responsibility for overseeing the implementation of the CSRD and for mobilizing the reporting process internally.

prompt reflection on aspects of work that might otherwise be seen as too mundane to mention. For example, I would ask, "What do you actually do during a typical day in this process?" and "What do you use to do it?" I also asked targeted questions about specific documents - such as templates or annexes - particularly when they had not been brought up spontaneously. These documents were not treated as standalone objects of analysis, but as entry points for reconstructing the ongoing negotiations and practical work of reporting. Following Asdal & Reinertsen (2022, p. 172), I was interested less in the formal content of the documents than in how the informants related to them, navigated them, and integrated them into their daily work.

The interview guide was structured around three main parts: a warm-up, a thematic core, and a concluding section. The warm-up focused on context and role - asking participants to describe their organization, their responsibilities, and how far along they were in the CSRD process. I often opened by asking them to describe a regular workday within the reporting process. Their responses typically revealed what aspects of the process were most salient to them - whether it was the disruption of normal workflows, the sense-making efforts required, or the practical tools and procedures involved. These early answers helped shape the order and focus of the themes I followed in each conversation. While I had identified several core themes in advance - such as internal structures, collaboration networks, data flows, and document use - I remained flexible, letting informants guide the direction of discussion, with slight steering from me if needed. This balance allowed me to explore what mattered most to them, while still pursuing the analytical questions I brought to the field. Follow-up questions were central to this approach, often including prompts like "what does that mean in practice?" or "can you give an example?" The concluding section circled back to the broader picture. I asked about what they saw as the main rewards and challenges of the CSRD process, and whether there was anything else they wanted to share that we hadn't touched on.

Although I attempted snowball sampling in the first four cases, participants often recommended individuals I had already contacted. Interestingly, I noticed a pattern: CSOs with technical backgrounds tended to suggest others with similar training, while those with backgrounds in economics or finance pointed toward peers with the same type of expertise. This became a small but telling observation in itself - it suggested that people may often stay within their own professional circles when thinking about who is relevant to this work.

3.2.3 Conducting the Interviews and Transcription

In line with Kvale (2007, p. 69), I began each interview by introducing myself, presenting the project and its purpose, and offering space for any questions before we began. My goal was to ensure that informants felt at ease and understood both the topic and their role in the study. I sought to balance adherence to the interview guide with attentiveness to each informant's tone, narrative, and emphasis. Given the exploratory nature of the study and the novelty of the CSRD, I revised the interview guide throughout the fieldwork. This iterative process enhanced my sensitivity to emerging themes and helped refine the analytical lens. For example, during the second interview, the topic of inter-sectoral collaboration networks was raised - prompting

me to explore this theme in subsequent interviews.

Voluntary participation and informed consent were central to the study. All participants were informed of the project's purpose and their rights prior to the interview. Each received a formal information sheet from SIKT detailing data handling and protocol and their right to withdraw at any time. These rights were reiterated verbally before the interview, and explicit consent to record was obtained. In some cases, participants were later given the opportunity to review quotations or clarify meaning via follow-up emails, in line with NESH's emphasis on avoiding misrepresentation and protecting participant dignity (NESH, 2024, p. 12–13).

While digital interviews may limit rapport-building and restrict access to body language cues, they also allowed participants to join from familiar environments, such as their offices or homes, which may have enhanced their comfort. In a few cases, participants shared their screens to walk me through documents or internal processes, offering valuable insights. Despite the limitations of the digital format, participants appeared engaged and responded openly and thoughtfully to the questions. All interviews were recorded using the University of Oslo-approved Nettskjema dictaphone tool, with prior informed consent. The recordings were transcribed automatically using the built-in Autotekst function, and then manually reviewed and corrected for accuracy. Transcripts were exported as .txt files and imported into NVivo for coding and analysis. All data was stored securely on a local, encrypted device and will be deleted by 05.05.2025, in accordance with NESH guidance (NESH, 2024, p. 14).

Although I coded initially emerging themes after transcribing interviews, these were more so functional categories, such the specific assessments being referenced, organizational structure, creation of teams etc. After each interview, I maintained a reflective log where I noted initial impressions, uncertainties, and analytical leads. This practice allowed me to treat interpretation as an ongoing process rather than something to be reserved for the end. The emerging themes were continually cross-referenced with CSRD documents, creating a dialogue between interview material and the documents. This journal served as a tool for transparency and accountability, as recommended by (NESH, 2024, p. 10), and helped me track how insights developed over time. While the project includes a journal for reflexivity, further strategies for quality assurance are needed (NESH, 2024, p. 11). To do this, I have decided to triangulate my sources, through cross-referencing interview data and key regulatory documents. This allowed me to test the consistency of informants statements and clarify or challenge my interpretations. While I did not conduct member validation (Kvale, 2007, p. 103), my questions were guided by answers from previous interviews, so I did gain a possibility to discuss preliminary findings, however the most important step was I took careful steps - such as sending clarifying follow-up mails - to ensure accuracy and respectful representations of participant's opinions and experiences. The iterative coding rounds also helped in quality assurance in this process, making sure that understandings were constantly adapted based on new findings.

The coding process turned out to be far more complex and time-consuming than I had anticipated. I found myself re-coding and revisiting transcripts multiple times in light of both new interviews and evolving interpretations of key documents. The CSOs I interviewed represented a wide range of professional backgrounds, organizational structures,

and perspectives on sustainability reporting. Preserving this multiplicity - rather than reducing it to a singular "truth" - required sustained engagement and analytical flexibility. My initial assumptions were frequently challenged, and the layered, often opaque nature of the CSRD (as many informants themselves emphasized) demanded a gradual building of understanding. This informs my key aims for this thesis: first, to make the dynamics and complexities of the CSRD more accessible and understandable; and second, to retain the diversity of perspectives among the CSOs I spoke with, while still pointing to patterns and tensions they shared.

Although the case is locally situated in Norway, the thesis is written in English. As a result, all interviewees had to be translated from Norwegian, which carries the risk of losing some of the original meaning - particularly cultural references or linguistic nuance (Birbili, 2000). I have aimed to minimize this risk by carefully reviewing each translation and, where relevant, including explanatory footnotes to preserve important subtleties. Both the transcription and analysis were carried out with attention to these challenges, in order to accurately reflect the perspectives and practices of the informants and to uphold ethical and credible research standards.

3.3 Documents as Secondary Data

To complement this interview material and deepen my understanding of how sustainability reporting under the CSRD is structured and enacted, I conducted a document analysis inspired by Asdal and Reinertsen's (2022) practice-oriented approach. In line with their framework, I treated documents not as passive reflections of an external reality, but as active participants in shaping sustainability work.

Asdal and Reinertsen's (2022, pp. 102-123) analytical turn of "document issues" helped me deepen my understanding of the agency that documents possess - how they come into being, in what contexts, and how they contribute to the modification of what sustainability is and how it should be acted upon. Documents do this by presenting methods for action and drawing together diverse elements to form an argument (Asdal & Reinertsen, 2022, p. 104). While I considered other analytical perspectives, such as documents as tools or document movements, I found these dimensions were already well addressed through the analytical tools afforded by ANT and valuation studies. In contrast, approaching documents as engaging in *issue modification work* aligned more directly with my empirical material and offered a lens that complemented my existing repertoire of tools (Asdal & Reinertsen, 2022, p. 111). From this perspective, issues are not static: they undergo modification as documents evolve across time and institutional contexts, sometimes generating new versions of an issue or rendering it invisible altogether (Asdal & Reinertsen, 2022). The documents I analyzed were thus not static texts, but dynamic sites where sustainability is enacted, organizational roles are reconfigured, and reporting practices are continuously shaped in real time.

My relationship to these documents evolved over time. I engaged with them before, during, and after the interviews, and each informed my understanding of the other. Early readings of the directive helped shape the interview guide by highlighting areas where

organizational processes might vary - for example, how companies approach the double materiality assessment. After conducting interviews, I returned to the document with new eyes, now reading them in light of the practical realities the CSOs had described. This back-and-forth process was not always linear. At times, I followed tangents - reading amendments from the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD) to the CSRD, or tracing footnoted references to other EU strategies, regulations, and directives. These detours became part of the learning process, even if they did not all lead directly to material used in the final analysis. Over time, however, this broad engagement gave way to a more focused approach. Since my goal was to understand how CSRD implementation is unfolding in organizations, I concentrated on the documents most directly relevant to companies: the directive itself, its annex, the EFRAG spreadsheet template, and an internal presentation shared by one of the participating companies.

My approach to the documents was twofold. First, I read them directly to understand how they engage in *contexting* - that is, how they establish associations and draw together actors, institutions, and references to situate and modify the issue at hand (Asdal & Reinertsen, 2022, p. 117). This includes examining how the documents define sustainability, prescribe methodologies, and structure reporting practices. I traced the networks in which the documents are situated: Who created them? What actors and procedures were mobilized? What problems do they claim to solve, and through what mechanisms? My aim was to uncover the regulatory vision embedded in the CSRD - what it attempts to make visible and actionable. This ties directly into how the documents participate in issue modification: how they modify the problem of sustainability over time, introduce specific modes of intervention, and contribute to reshaping roles and practices (Asdal & Reinertsen, 2022, p. 111).

Second, I analyzed how these documents were interpreted, referenced and used by the CSOs I interviewed. Rather than conducting a comparative reading of how each informant interpreted the texts line-by-line, I looked for broader patterns in how participants described engaging with them. Were the documents seen as helpful, confusing, or overly rigid? What actions were enabled and what actions were constricted? How did informants relate to them in their day-to-day work? This allowed me to reflect on the documents' indirect effects - how they circulate through organizations and shape practice, not only through what they explicitly state, but also through how they are understood, questioned, or adapted. A recurring theme across interviews was the friction between the detailed documents and practitioner's lived experiences. While materials were intended to clarify expectations, not one CSO reported them having a clarifying or enlightening effect. This gap between the formal structure of the directive and the everyday experience of working with it's contents proved analytically productive. It highlighted the force of the documents - how they prescribe actors, define relevance, and structure expectations - as well as their limits.

3.3.1 List of Documents

The documents selected for analysis are all official and publicly available materials that form the core of the CSRD's legal and technical infrastructure. These documents were not randomly

selected, but rather identified as central to how sustainability is framed, operationalized, and communicated within the new regulatory framework. Their form, language, and structure played a direct role in shaping the types of work and expertise needed to engage with sustainability reporting, as can be seen in Table 3.2.

3.3.2 My Role as a Researcher

Kvale (2007, p. 36) uses a metaphor to describe two contrasting approaches to qualitative interviewing: the interviewer as a miner, who digs for objective facts, and the interviewer as a traveler, who co-produces knowledge by moving through a field of meaning with their informants. These metaphors are not mutually exclusive but serve as a reminder to reflect on how knowledge is produced, and to examine the assumptions that shape the interview process. While I set out to understand specific aspects of CSRD implementation, my aim was not to uncover fixed truths, but to explore how a transnational framework comes to take shape in the local practices of the Norwegian real estate sector. Some aspects of this were more concrete - such as assessment tools or reporting spreadsheets - but much of it involved navigating an unfolding, uncertain terrain.

This project is grounded in STS, which places particular emphasis on the role of the researcher in shaping the research process (Haraway, 1988). I approached this work with an openness to learning, as a sociologist with limited prior knowledge to accounting, reporting, or EU regulation. This was a methodological choice. By working in unfamiliar territory, I aimed to resist the temptation of grand narratives. Instead, I let the material guide me. Each interview and document reading revealed new tensions, logics, and questions. Only after sustained engagement with the material did I begin to see which analytical tools could help me make sense of what I was observing. Staying open to uncertainty throughout the process was both challenging and deeply rewarding.

This thesis does not aim to evaluate or rank companies or reporting strategies. Rather, I view my role as offering a situated account of how sustainability reporting is shaped by documents, systems, and professional judgments. Positioning myself as a "traveler" helped reinforce this perspective: I aimed not to point out failings, but to understand the practical challenges and negotiations involved in translating the CSRD into everyday work. My goal is to present a nuanced account that is attentive to competing demands, institutional constraints, and the varying capacities of those tasked with implementation. While I hope this research supports more grounded and realistic approaches in sustainability reporting, I recognize that it may be interpreted in ways I cannot fully control. To mitigate this, I have anonymized all informants and organizations, and I present all findings with contextual care, avoiding overgeneralization or prescriptive claims. This project is intended as a contribution to ongoing conversations about how sustainability is practiced, interpreted, and institutionalized - not as a definitive guide to how it should, or should not, be done.

3.3.3 Use of AI tools

I used ChatGPT at a few points during the thesis process. Primarily I used the tool as to help me make sense of emerging reflections, and to help me engage with what I was learning. This primarily took form on walks, where I would use the audio-function to have conversations. This could include me sharing reflections or understandings of concepts. One method was to ask the tool to either repeat back to me what I had said, which was a good method for hearing if my thoughts had merit forcing me to re-formulate them if not. I always re-consulted documents and texts, which was what I would reflect on, afterwards to make sure that I was critically assessing the outputs of this process. Another way this tool has helped me has been in writing code for formatting this thesis. I decided to write it using the coding language LaTeX, which resulted in me having to learn various coding-commands as I went. In this sense, ChatGPT functioned as a tool to help me clarify thinking. I always engaged with this tool in a critical and reflective manor, and all final interpretations, arguments, and formulations are my own.

Table 3.2: Key documents included in the analysis

Document Name	Type / Source	Date	Purpose and Role in Analysis
Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council	EU Directive	Dec 2022	Establishes the legal foundation for the CSRD; outlining its scope, objectives, and key definitions. In this thesis, it is primarily used to contextualize the regulatory framework and examine how sustainability is framed as a legal and institutional issue. While not highly technical, it plays a role in issue modification by shaping the problem space that subsequent documents seek to operationalize. (Directive 2022/2464/EU)
Annex I of Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772	Regulatory Annex	Oct 2023	Contains the detailed disclosure requirements, reporting formats, and definitions that operationalize the CSRD. It serves as the technical backbone of the framework, prescribing how assessments should be conducted and how sustainability information should be structured and disclosed. (EU 2023/2772, 2023)
EFRAG Implementation Guidance 3 – List of ESRS Data Points	EFRAG Guidance / Template	Feb 2024	A spreadsheet functioning as a reporting template, listing the required data points and indicating how companies are expected to structure their disclosures. It supports the practical implementation of the standards by translating abstract requirements into a tabular format for data collection and internal coordination. (EFRAG IG 3, 2024)
Internal presentation (procedure outline) from participating company	Internal Document	Mar 2024	Outlined how one firm organizes stakeholder engagement as part of its CSRD-related assessments. It provided concrete procedural steps that offered depth to the interview material and allowed for comparison between practices.

Note: Although only Implementation Guide 3 (IG 3) is directly analyzed in this thesis, some illustrations from EFRAG IG 1 are also used to clarify how the reporting infrastructure is presented and communicated. These Implementation Guides (IGs) are not new legal documents, but simplified and structured reformulations of Annex I aimed at aiding implementation.

Chapter 4

Analysis

The CSRD did not emerge in a vacuum. It builds on earlier directives, strategies from the European Commission, and rounds of public consultation. This chapter begins not with its origins, but with the moment the directive starts to take shape as a mobilizing force beyond the halls of Brussels - when it begins to link actors, modify issues, and establish paths for information to move. I follow how the directive mobilizes participation, organizes valuation practices, and connects (or disconnects) actors, documents, and data flows across contexts.

Before moving into the analysis, I briefly map some of the key actors involved in implementing the CSRD. These actors occupy distinct yet overlapping positions in translating the directive into practice. *Chief Sustainability Officers (CSOs)* are internal figures - they typically carry the responsibility for coordinating sustainability efforts and producing the disclosures required by the directive. *Auditors*, in contrast, enter from the outside. Their task is to assess whether these disclosures meet formal assurance criteria, bringing with them standardized procedures and an authority over what counts as credible reporting. *Consultants* inhabit a more fluid space. They are often brought in to support interpretation, develop internal systems, or help translate regulatory demands into organizational routines. In this study, consultants were not always involved. Their presence was more common in larger firms, where they were typically drawn from audit or assurance backgrounds - blurring the boundary between advising and pre-assessing. In two smaller companies, CSOs also engaged external help, but in these cases from niche ESG consultancies. This likely reflects the CSOs' own orientations: their work was less technical and more focused on narrative-building and stakeholder engagement, shaping the kinds of expertise they found useful.

This analysis unfolds in two parts, each tracing the journey of the CSRD. From the moment the directive begins circulating through templates, standards, and systems, it doesn't just inform practice it helps shape what sustainability work becomes. Along this journey, themes of connection and disconnection become central: the CSRD links together actors, knowledge, and practices, while also producing breaks, tensions, and exclusions.

4.1 Framing the Issue and Designing the Solution

Before analysing how the CSRD defines the problem it sets out to solve, it is worth pausing to consider the world one enters when first encountering the directive. A simple online search for "CSRD" yields a sprawling terrain: dozens of consultancy websites offering guides, checklists, and interpretations tools (Deloitte, 2023; KPMG Assurance and Consulting Services LLP, 2022; PwC, n.d.) ; webinars promising to break down the directive's requirements (Arbeidsgiverforeningen Spekter, 2024; Klimapartnere, 2024); and tech-companies advertising digital systems for collecting, transforming, and reporting sustainability data (Position Green, 2024; SustainLab, 2024; Workiva, 2024). Alongside this growing ecosystem of intermediaries sit the formal instruments: the CSRD directive itself, annexes and delegated acts authored by the European Commission (EC), The European Parliament and the Council (Directive 2022/2464/EU ; EU 2023/2772 (2023) ; Commission (2023)), implementation guidelines and European Sustainability Reporting Standards developed by EFRAG (EFRAG, 2023, 2024b; European Commission, 2023; EFRAG IG 3, 2024). National governments, too, play a role, translating the directive into domestic legal frameworks (Verdipapirlovutvalget, 2023), perhaps with a few changes, perhaps not (PwC Global, 2025). Each entry point share a common theme: an attempt to make sense of uncertainty. What, precisely, must be reported? How should it be measured? Who decides what is material?

This uncertainty unfolds within a broader world shaped by financial accounting. Annual reports, external audits, internal control systems, and investor-facing disclosures have long formed the backbone of corporate reporting. In this world, auditability and comparison is paramount to credibility. Concepts such as materiality, risk, and assurance have technical definitions and institutional routines. Through the CSRD, this world of financial reporting is beginning to overlap with another: the situated and often practical work of sustainability professionals. This includes managing construction materials, energy use, waste systems and workplace safety. These domains have historically operated with different logics and devices. As the CSRD begins to draw them together - introducing new associations. What, then, is the issue the CSRD sets out to address? This section traces how the directive engages in issue modification work (Asdal & Reinertsen, 2022): reshaping what sustainability is and how it should be acted upon through the construction of reporting frameworks. It also examines how the directive mobilizes actors into its vision and how tensions emerge as its requirements enter everyday organizational life.

4.1.1 The Transparency Gap

This section lays the foundation for what follows by tracing how the CSRD modifies the issue it sets out to solve. At its core, the directive states that sustainability is an issue of transparency, however, not in the sense of simply disclosing more information. Rather, it is about producing legible and comparable information that can enable accountability, build investor confidence, and steer capital toward sustainable activities. Drawing on Asdal and Reinertsens (2022) notion of issue modification, I treat the CSRD not as a neutral reflection of sustainability concerns, but as a device that reshaped them through reporting practices.

In order to understand the specific issue formulations within the CSRD, it is worth recalling the broader policy landscape in which the directive is situated. As part of the European Green Deal and the Action Plan on Financing Sustainable Growth (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 1 ; rec. 2), the CSRD contributes to the EU's wider strategy for addressing climate change by aligning financial regulation with long-term environmental goals (Council of the European Union, 2025; European Commission, 2018). Rising global temperatures are modified to be not only an issue pertaining to ecological crisis, but as a systemic risk to economic and social stability (European Commission, 2019). In response, the EC calls for a fundamental shift in how sustainability is assessed, valued, and reported. A key part of this transformation is the mobilization of financial markets (European Commission, 2019): steering capital toward sustainability investments through increased transparency, standardized reporting, and long-term thinking. The CSRD supports this ambition by introducing requirements for external verification and audit, aiming to enhance the credibility of sustainability disclosures (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 5 ; rec. 13) and position them as legitimate inputs into financial decision-making.

Within this broader policy context, the CSRD begins to define the specific problem it aims to solve - one that translates high-level ambitions into a specific regulatory framework. One such formulation appears in the directive's reference to an *information gap* (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 15). According to the directive, companies do not produce sufficient or comparable information about their environmental and social impacts, making it difficult for external stakeholders, and companies themselves, to engage in meaningful accountability processes (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 9). This absence of comparable, trustworthy information is thus positioned as contributing to an *accountability deficit*, where affected publics lack the the information needed to scrutinize, evaluate, or contest corporate conduct (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 14).

The directive identifies two main consequences of the information gap that results from insufficient sustainability disclosures. These consequences are linked to different groups of what the directive refers to as *users* of sustainability information (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 9), and help explain how the lack of data contributes to what is framed as an accountability deficit. The first identified user of sustainability information is civil society. It notes that when access to sustainability information is limited, democratic oversight is weakened, and trade unions and workers' representatives are less able to participate meaningfully in corporate governance processes (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 9). The second group is investors. Here, the concern is that a lack of comparable and reliable data can lead to poor investment decisions and even contribute to broader financial instability (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 9 ; rec. 11). Taken together, these concerns construct the information gap not merely as a technical reporting issue, but as a challenge to accountability, financial stability, and public trust in how companies are expected to balance profit-making with social and environmental responsibility (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 14).

While the directive highlights the importance of transparency for society and financial markets, it also emphasized what companies stand to gain. In this framing, companies are presented as

beneficiaries of the reporting process, rather than solely being forced report. The directive outlines several internal advantages associated with high-quality sustainability reporting. One example is improved access to financial capital, especially since the financial sector increasingly treats sustainability as a source of value (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 12), leading to the creation and marketing of financial offerings - such as green bonds, ESG rated funds, and sustainability-linked loans, all built around environmental and social claims. The directive also highlights benefits such as better identification and management of risks and opportunities. The directive also suggest that reporting can improve engagement with stakeholders, such as employees, unions, NGOs, and consumers, by creating more structured channels for sharing sustainability information. In doing so, it is expected to support dialogue, enhance corporate reputation, and reduce the burden of responding to individual information requests (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 12). Rather than presenting sustainability reporting solely as a regulatory obligation, sustainability reporting is framed as a strategic asset for the companies themselves.

Beneath these claims about both external and internal benefits lies a deeper, unifying logic: transparency. Under the CSRD, transparency is framed as a way of enabling a wide range of actors to act more effectively. Investors are expected to make better-informed decisions; civil society and policymakers are given tools to hold companies more accountable; and citizens and savers are framed as beneficiaries of a more stable and inclusive economic system (Directive 2022/2464/EU) Yet, even as environmental governance becomes increasingly dependent on data, through growing demands for metrics, indicators, and quantifiable disclosures, the production of more information does not automatically lead to greater transparency or accountability (Freidberg, 2020; Ghosh & Faxon, 2023). This shift builds on two underlying assumptions. First, that sustainability can be achieved by measuring harms and risks and that more measurement will lead to better knowledge, which in turn enables more rational and targeted action. Second, that translating diverse sustainability practices into commensurable forms makes them more manageable, that once something is made visible, it can be monitored and acted upon. In this logic, visibility leads to transparency, and transparency becomes the basis for accountability.

In the CSRD, transparency is pursued through data-driven frameworks built on metrics, indicators, and standardized disclosures. These frameworks are often presented as neutral tools for capturing reality. Yet, what gets measured, and how, is never straightforward. As studies in climate governance have shown, metrics do not merely record environmental conditions; they also reflect and reinforce institutional priorities, shaping which issues become legible, and therefore actionable (McElwee, 2017; Nost, 2019, 2022). The investment in metrics and standardized disclosures reflects what Laurent (2022) describes as the European project of harmonization: the effort to make objects uniform through appeals to scientific objectivity, enabling their circulation across contexts and contributing to cohesion. This investment includes the development of shared tools and practices aimed at gathering and formulating sustainability information in consistent ways. While this may appear to produce legibility such standardization can also obscure context. In this way, the CSRD does not merely call for transparency; it enacts a politics of visibility, determining what is seen, what is counted, and what is excluded.

Valuation studies offer a productive lens for analyzing how the CSRD frames sustainability as both a reporting challenge and a financial concern. Rather than treating values such as accountability or transparency as neutral aims, these studies show how such values are constructed through devices, classifications, and institutional routines (Fourcade, 2011; Muniesa, 2012). Two core valuations are embedded in the design of the CSRD. First, that sustainability information, once standardized and made legible, can serve as a mechanism for holding unsustainable companies accountable. Second, that sustainability is not only an issue of environmental or social harm, but a potential source of systemic risk to the financial system if left unmeasured and unmanaged (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec.14). Through what Asdal and Reinertsen (2022) term *issue-modification*, valuation devices such as disclosure templates reconfigure sustainability issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss, labor violations into legible reports for external users. These reports are framed in terms of attracting capital, mitigating systemic financial risk, and reinforcing trust in the EU social market economy. In this way, the CSRD does not simply promote transparency; it reshapes the lenses through which sustainability is measured, seen, and valued.

In this way, the CSRD operates not only as a policy instrument, but as a valuation device that does more than describe a problem; it helps construct it. It positions finance as both *exposed* to sustainability risks and *instrumental in managing them*, citing an estimated need for an additional €260 billion in investment every year to meet climate targets (European Commission, 2019). On the one hand, unsustainable practices are framed as potential threats to financial stability; on the other, financial markets and the steering of capital as key for increasing sustainable activities. The directive integrates both new and existing actors into a network of disclosure and verification aimed at restoring visibility, trust, and control. What emerges is not merely a call for more data, but a reliance on the assumption that making sustainability legible to capital is a necessary pathway for managing environmental and social futures. This process of issue modification, in turn, sets the stage for examining how actors are assembled to respond and how they become aligned with the directive's logic and participate in its formation.

4.1.1.1 Reconfiguring a Solution: Accounting, Auditing, and Rituals of Control

In the previous section, I traced how the CSRD constructs sustainability as an issue of transparency and accountability. This section shifts focus to the actors brought in to make that information reliable. The methods for collecting, transforming, and verifying sustainability information are largely drawn from the fields of financial accounting and auditing - further setting the stage for understanding how the CSRD is structured as a solution. To analyze this process, I draw on the concept of *mobilization* (Latour, 1990), which helps illuminate how the CSRD becomes a working network of aligned people, tools, and knowledge. In addressing the related challenges of closing the information gap and channeling capital toward environmental goals, the directive engages actors long associated with the production and verification of financial information - reconfiguring them into a new system of managing and measuring sustainability issues.

The European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG) has traditionally acted as the ECs technical advisor on financial reporting standards. With the introduction of the CSRD, EFRAG's mandate was expanded to include the development of the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) (Directive 2022/2464/EU ; EFRAG (n.d.)). To support the integration of financial disclosures with sustainability concerns, EFRAG mobilized a broad range of actors through public consultations (EFRAG, 2024a) and through the development of two new teams composed of specialists in environmental, social and human rights reporting, business conduct and technical standard-setting (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 39 ; EFRAG (2024c)). As a result, EFRAG now operates with a dual structure: maintaining its advisory role in financial reporting while also developing sustainability standards and offering technical guidance to support CSRD implementation. EFRAG is funded through a combination of EU support and private sector contributions (EFRAG, n.d.), with the directive emphasizing the importance of public funding to ensure the organization's independence and ability to serve the broader European public interest (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 39).

Through this expanded role, EFRAG acts as a key node in the CSRD's broader network of actor mobilization. It not only designs the reporting structure but provides interpretive guidance and implementation tools, including Q&A documents and educational resources (EFRAG, n.d.). By doing so, EFRAG helps align sustainability reporting with the procedural logic of financial reporting, while also seeking to make that knowledge more accessible and usable for those tasked with implementation. This actor alignment through mobilization is a part of the broader strategy to embed sustainability within existing systems of financial regulation. The standards EFRAG develops directly define how companies are expected to disclose sustainability-related information by establishing the metrics and methodologies that determine what gains visibility and priority in the final report. In her study of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) Chiapello 2016 shows how such standards reflect and reinforce a shift in how companies are evaluated - privileging the perspectives and interests of financial actors. This entanglement of sustainability with the logic of standardized reporting will be explored more in the section on ESRS.

While EFRAG and the ESRS define what information should be reported and how, auditors are mobilized within the CSRD network to verify its contents. Their role is central to ensuring data reliability and preventing companies portraying themselves to be more sustainable than they are (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 13). The directive outlines a gradual increase in verification demands. Until 2028, verification requirements will remain limited, typically involving less intensive procedures and taking the form of a negative statement - such as "nothing has come to our attention." After 2028, however, auditors will be expected to conduct more thorough testing and provide a positive verification opinion on the accuracy of reported sustainability information (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 65). The directive also extends key rules from financial auditing to this new domain - including requirements for auditor independence and the consistency of results across companies (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 72-74). In addition, auditors are tasked with ensuring that sustainability and financial reporting are not treated as separate processes or outcomes, but as interconnected forms of information that speak to and inform one another (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 66).

The role of auditors becomes interesting when approached through Latour's 1986 concept of *centers of calculation*. These are sites where knowledge is accumulated, organized, and made actionable through circulation of representations produced elsewhere. These centers operate by turning local, situated realities into standardized formats that can be compared, evaluated, and acted upon at a distance. In the context of the CSRD, auditors help enable this process by verifying the representations companies produce. Although these representations stem from vastly different domains - emissions data, human rights abuses, governance procedures - they are made comparable through a shared reporting format. Auditors play a key role in the translation of diverse and situated sustainability issues into standardized formats, making them comparable within a shared reporting framework. As both translators, and gatekeepers in the formalized procedures of CSRD reporting, they are central not only to verifying information but also to shaping how the directive is interpreted and put into practice. For many companies, the CSRD does not become legible through the directive documents alone, but through the work of auditors and consultants who act as translators - turning complex regulatory texts into procedures and checklists.

The CSRD is not just a matter of compliance; it is something that must be *done*. Companies are responsible for gathering sustainability data, making judgments about what is relevant, and determining how that information should be presented. In this process, auditors often become both the first point of contact and the final arbiter. From their position in centers of calculation, they occupy a privileged role - one that enables them to determine whether the realities described by companies are credible, compliant, and *correct*. Before turning to how companies engage with the task of reporting, however, we must take a closer look at the specific tools and standards CSRD assigns to guide this work.

4.1.2 What Gets In, What Gets Out: The Filtering Logics of Materiality

A key shift introduced by the CSRD is the integration of sustainability reporting into existing systems and procedures for financial disclosures. This is evident not only in institutional overlaps - such as EFRAG's role in standard-setting- but also in how sustainability reporting is increasingly embedded within the architecture of financial reporting itself. Through requirements such as joint auditing and integration within annual reports, but also in sharing similar conceptual foundations. One of the most significant of these is double materiality (DM). This section examines what DM is, where it comes from and how it asserts agency. Building on the previous section's discussion of how the CSRD frames sustainability as something that must be made visible and comparable across contexts, this section turns to the mechanisms through which relevance is defined and priority is set.

To understand this conceptual shift, it is useful to first outline the analytical lens from valuation studies that informs this section. While the previous chapter approached valuation as a performative process - where value is enacted through social and technical practices, I now focus on a specified process within this: the translation of social and environmental concerns into formats compatible with monetary value. Complex and often incommensurable phenomena, such as nature, risk, or responsibility, are not new to being made visible and

European sustainability reporting standards (ESRS)

ESRS 1	General requirements
ESRS 2	General disclosures
ESRS E1	Climate change
ESRS E2	Pollution
ESRS E3	Water and marine resources
ESRS E4	Biodiversity and ecosystems
ESRS E5	Resource use and circular economy
ESRS S1	Own workforce
ESRS S2	Workers in the value chain
ESRS S3	Affected communities
ESRS S4	Consumers and end-users
ESRS G1	Business conduct

Figure 4.1: Overview of ESRS Sustainability Matters

Excerpt from the ESRS topic hierarchy used in materiality assessments. These are the topics that companies must assess for materiality under both the impact and financial lenses. Each topic includes a range of sub-topics and sub-sub-topics, and is accompanied by specific Application Requirements (ARs) that guide how materiality should be determined and disclosed.

actionable to financial actors or valuations (Fourcade, 2011). We will retain the performative dimension of valuation processes, with an added emphasis on how these devices not only extend financial logics of measurement, but also actively shape what is recognized, prioritized, and rendered reportable in the CSRD framework.

Before diving into the concept of Double Materiality, one final stop is needed on our way there: the origins and function of materiality as it is understood in financial accounting. Materiality is a foundational concept used to determine whether a piece of information is significant enough to influence the decisions of users of the financial reports - typically investors, but also including regulators, and analysts. Under this logic, any detail that could reasonably affect such decisions must be disclosed, following established reporting standards (Harvard Business School, 2021); in the CSRD these are the ESRS. What qualifies as material varies, but the underlying logic remains: if excluding a piece of information could mislead users, it must be reported (Harvard Business School, 2021). Crucially, materiality is not a fixed threshold, rather, it is shaped through professional judgment. Auditors assess materiality early

in the audit process to determine which elements, such as account balances or transactions, require closer examination. These judgments reflect assumptions about what users are likely to find relevant and are expected to shift as new information emerges (KPMG Assurance and Consulting Services LLP, 2022). In this way, materiality operates as a dynamic and situational filter, shaping not only what is verified, but what is considered worth knowing.

The concept of materiality, as described above, closely aligns with other principles we have encountered in tracing the CSRD - particularly the idea that sustainability information is intended to serve users by enabling well-informed decisions. Not only does the CSRD draw on this principle, but also expands it into the concept of *double materiality* (Directive 2022/2464/EU, Rec. 22 ; (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.3)). This framework introduces two distinct perspectives that determine whether information should be disclosed: *impact materiality*, and *financial materiality*. Each must be considered in evaluating what information may influence user decisions.

* Financial materiality is used here in the broad sense of affecting the value of the company, not just in the sense of affecting financial measures recognised in the financial statements.

Figure 4.2: Illustration of double materiality as presented by the EC.¹ On the right, impact materiality is shown as an outward-facing arrow from the company to the plane. Indicating how corporate activities affect society and the environment. On the left, financial materiality is depicted as an inward-facing arrow, highlighting how external sustainability factors can affect the company’s financial performance. A left-pointing connects the two, suggesting that environmental and social impacts may, under certain conditions, become financially material.

To understand this shift, it is helpful to briefly revisit how sustainability has traditionally been assessed. Historically, the dominant approach has been what the CSRD now terms impact materiality , or the "inside-out" perspective ² that examines how a company’s activities affect the world around it. This includes environmental degradation, labor conditions, and broader social consequences. Impact materiality keeps the lens outward facing, requiring companies to assess how their operations affect people and the environment - not only directly, but across

²While the terms “outside-in” and “inside-out” are not used in the CSRD or ESRS texts, they were frequently employed by informants to refer to financial and impact materiality, respectively.

their entire value chain, including indirect and non-contractual business relationships (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.4). This encompasses a wide spectrum of sustainability matters, from labor conditions and emissions to biodiversity loss and community impacts. So the outward-facing perspective is not new, but its relation to materiality is. The CSRD aims to connect environmental, social and governance (ESG) concerns with a decision-usefulness logic. For example: what kinds of negative social impacts - such as poor labor conditions - might lead consumers to avoid a company's product? What harms to local wildlife could influence regulators to impose stricter protections? These reflect the kinds of actual or potential impacts that companies are expected to identify and assess when determining material matters under the impact materiality process (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App.A, AR. 9). In this way, *impact materiality* translates broad concerns into factors that could influence user-decisions. Through this logic, we can begin to trace how the CSRD introduces *valuation devices* that transform complex and often qualitative sustainability issues into user-relevant information.

But for these valuation logics to work, something else is needed: sustainability concerns have to be made visible and easy to communicate in ways that make sense to outside users. Many sustainability impacts are hard to see directly. We don't see a carbon footprint with our own eyes - we see numbers in reports or entries in spreadsheets. These are what Latour 1990 calls inscriptions: representations that make distant or complex things understandable and usable for decision-making. Just like climate models, these representations are not a simple one-to-one translation from phenomenon to paper - they are built through careful work, where data is selected, translated, and shaped to fit into standard formats. For the CSRD, this work is essential. Companies are expected to turn environmental and social issues into information that is comparable and actionable. While some data points may be relatively straightforward, such as how many employees are entitled to sick leave, or how much energy is used from renewable versus non-renewable sources. Others, as we will come to see, require much more representational work to be made visible. Tools like materiality matrices and audit tables don't just organize data. They simplify and flatten complex realities so that they can move through financial and regulatory systems. In this way, sustainability becomes "real" not because it exists independently, but because it is made legible to the institutions meant to act on it.

This work of representation doesn't just make sustainability concerns visible in a general sense - it adds additional layers of translation through which sustainability comes to be legible. One way the CSRD introduces an additional layer is through its of the double materiality perspective. In addition to the more traditional outward-facing lens for representing sustainability, another perspective is added, one that shifts focus inward: *financial materiality*, or the "outside-in" perspective. This approach considers how external sustainability factors - such as climate change, regulatory shifts, biodiversity loss, or supply chain instability - may affect a company's operations, profitability, and long-term financial performance (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.5). Using the same examples from impact materiality, the perspective shifts as follows: How might social harms in the supply chain disrupt its efficiency, and what financial costs would be involved in quickly sourcing an alternative supplier? Or: What harms to local wildlife could lead to the depletion of key environmental resources and, in turn, disrupt the company's operations or increase costs in ways that affect its future cash flows?(EU 2023/2772,

2023, AR. 14)³

Financial materiality therefore plays a key role in making sustainability legible to financial actors. It works as a valuation device that helps translate complex and often incommensurable issues - like labor abuses or ecosystem degradation - into information that can be assessed in financial terms. Through this logic of valuation, issues tied to sustainability are made to signal potential financial vulnerabilities - becoming part of how corporate resilience and risk is assessed (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 2 SBM-3, DR. 48 (f)). The relevance of such information is determined by the "likelihood of occurrence and the potential magnitude of the financial effects" (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.5.51). In other words, a sustainability matter is considered financially material, and thereby relevant, if it is expected to impact a company's financial position, performance, cash flows, cost of capital, or access to finance over time (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.5.51). In this way, the CSRD modifies sustainability not only as an ethical or regulatory issue, but as something that must be made visible to capital. By *flattening*⁴ (Latour, 1990) environmental and social concerns through financial valuation logics, the CSRD activates valuation processes that reclassify these issues as worthy of attention - and potentially, of mitigation - if they are deemed financially meaningful. This dynamic of flattening through financial valuation logics is also illustrated in 4.2, which visualizes the distinction between financial and impact materiality. Although both materiality types are represented, the layout subtly emphasized the financial perspective - framing social and environmental impacts as relevant not only in their own terms, but also through their potential financial implications. This reflects a broader dynamic of financialization (Chiapello, 2015; Engen & Asdal, 2024a), where sustainability thus becomes visible not only as an ethical or political matter, but as a value in market-oriented sense: rendered into a commensurable form that can be recognized, evaluated, and acted upon by financial actors. This process will be further elaborated on in the discussion of forward-looking assumptions in Part 2.

In sum, the double materiality framework provides the conceptual starting point for how sustainability becomes reportable within the CSRD. By filtering environmental and social concerns through both impact and financial lenses, the directive redefines not only what counts as relevant information, but also how that relevance is established. This filtering process is not purely technical or objective - it depends on the construction of legibility through inscriptions: tables, matrices, and indicators that translate diffuse phenomena into forms that can be acted upon. These inscriptions are not neutral; they are authored, most notably by EFRAG, through standard-setting and consultation processes that embed specific ways of seeing and valuing sustainability. Sustainability does not enter reports as a self-evident truth; it is made real and actionable through representational labor, through valuation devices that render social and environmental matters legible to financial actors and regulators. Double materiality thus functions not only as a conceptual anchor, but as a performative structure that enables this

³Written in the language of the ESRS, this might be formulated as: *What harms to local wildlife could reasonably be expected to result in the depletion of natural capital, thereby contributing to a negative deviation in future expected cash inflows or an increase in future expected cash outflows due to reduced access to critical environmental resources required for the undertaking's operations*(EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App.A, AR. 14).

⁴Here, I draw on Latour's notion of "flattening" as a way of rendering heterogeneous concerns comparable and commensurable.

legibility. The representational labor that goes into this work will be hinted at in the last section of Part 1; setting the stage before we truly dive in to this process in Part 2 as we examine the work of other frameworks play a key role in translating these principles into practice.

4.1.2.1 From Ambition to Application: CSO Perspectives on Double Materiality

This section explores how Chief Sustainability Officers (CSOs) - the internal actors tasked with preparing sustainability disclosures - interpret and engage with the concept of double materiality (DM) in the context of the CSRD. While most informants expressed support for the directive's overall ambition in to accounting for both financial and impact-related dimensions of sustainability. There was, however, considerable variation in how they understood its practical implications. Some saw DM as a strategic tool for improving accountability and prioritization, while others described it as burdensome or misaligned with their everyday realities. These divergent perspectives offer an important empirical entry point into the valuation logic embedded in the CSRD: how it is taken up, translated, and sometimes resisted in practice. Rather than treating DM as a fixed or stable concept, this section traces how CSOs make sense of it in their own work, and how their interpretations both reinforce and challenge the directive's framing. The lines between DM and other elements of the CSRD - such as risk identification, forward-looking assessments, and resource planning - are often blurred in these accounts. These themes will be explored in more detail in Part 2, but here, DM serves as a starting point for examining how the directive is broadly perceived and how sustainability is being modified through everyday implementation.

The view of double materiality (DM) as a practical tool for improving sustainability work was strongly expressed by CSOs who framed it as a way to prioritize action and strengthen internal accountability. CSO4 and CSO9 both emphasized how DM could help direct attention to sustainability issues that are most relevant to the business. CSO9, who comes from a technical background, argued that failing to account for "the need for competitiveness and solid economic solutions... leads to very poor solutions that work against many other goals," and criticized older generations of environmental advocates for lacking holistic perspective. In a similar vein, CSO4 described materiality as essential for resource efficiency: "If we fail to identify what is truly material, we risk working on irrelevant sustainability issues, which would be a waste of resources."

These reflections do more than explain how DM functions - they reveal a deeper alignment with the valuation logic embedded in the CSRD. Both CSOs adopt the directive's core filtering mindset: that companies should focus on sustainability concerns that can be justified in terms of financial risk or operational impact. In this sense, DM becomes a tool for a more targeted and efficient sustainability management.

For other CSOs, DM was appealing not because it aligned with existing business logics, but because it created new openings to challenge them. CSO6, for instance, described years of pushing back against the assumption that profitability should always come first:

That's what motivates me: because that's what we've always been met with—'Yes,

but you also have to think about economic sustainability.' And my position has always been: that's already being thought about, so I don't need to focus on it.

Here, DM becomes a tactical resource - a way to translate environmental and social concerns into financial terms without losing their original substance. As CSO1 noted, it makes it harder for company leadership to "claim they didn't know", and CSO2 emphasized that it places these concerns "firmly on everyone's agenda - at the management level and also in finance." CSO6 offered perhaps the most comprehensive account of this shift:

I've been working with environment and sustainability in the industry for 18-20 years, and I've been in the industry for nearly 40 years, right? So I know—it's the bottom line that counts, and traditionally, the bottom line has only been about economics. So the fact that we're now tying sustainability, environment, nature, and human issues together with the financial—that's something I feel very positive about.

For these CSOs, DM is not simply about reporting. It is about modifying what counts as valuable. It offers a way to bring sustainability closer to the center of corporate valuation, whether by creating grounds for a more legitimized prioritization of concerns, shifting accountability upward towards management, or leveraging the language of finance to make sustainability harder to ignore.

Yet this same process of translation - of making sustainability visible through financial categories - was not without its challenges. Many CSOs who embraced the ambition of DM also described the difficulty of working across professional domains, particularly between sustainability and finance. As CSO11 reflected:

There's a lot we don't understand about the financial language and how things are now being set up in a kind of auditor-like way - things we haven't previously considered, like carbon quotas and other factors that we haven't really looked at together before. I'm sure it all makes sense, but it's still difficult.

This sense of disorientation was echoed by others. Several described the process as "not exactly a science - it feels very subjective (CSO3), and questioned the reliance on "fictive numbers" that don't result in "anything real anyway" (CSO10). This was not just an expression of technical frustration, but also disconnect from the legitimacy of the reporting process itself, and more broadly, the benefits promised by the CSRD. The challenge in these accounts, was not just the technical complexity of the CSRD, but the feeling of being pushed into unfamiliar valuation logics that reshaped how sustainability work was understood and performed. As we will explore more thoroughly in part 2.

This tension was particularly visible in how responsibilities were divided between departments. In larger companies, some noted that "finance understands the methodology, but not the content. We complement each other" (CSO11), with the implication that each side brings something essential but insufficient in its own. Yet that sense of complementarity was often tempered by practical constraints. CSO3 and CSO5 remarked that they were essentially only "content providers," responsible for supplying data, while finance teams handled the actual

reporting. CSO11 concludes that although finance and sustainability complement each other "it's not easy in a busy workday. Because this is something that comes on top of everything else we're already doing." (CSO11).

What emerges is not only a question of coordination, but also one of translation across professional domains. As the CSRD's places emphasis on financial integration, sustainability professionals increasingly find themselves either positioned as content providers - delivering data for others to process - or required to frame their work in terms that resonate with auditors and finance departments. These terms that may feel unfamiliar, or even misaligned, with how sustainability has traditionally been understood and practiced.⁵

Despite broad support for the ambition behind the CSRD and its emphasis on DM, many CSOs voiced deep frustration with how it is constructed. The most consistent concern was that the administrative burden far exceed existing capacity, diverting away from substantive sustainability work. As CSO5 put it, "The idea is excellent. And I think it's absolutely necessary. But maybe we've gone a bit overboard with the cod liver oil in the implementation."⁶

Others echoed this sentiment, describing a disconnect between the directive's promise and their lived experience of it. CSO3 reflected:

I think it's far too complicated and extensive - compared to what I hoped this would contribute to. I had high expectations because I thought this would really help us do the right things. But now I feel like we don't have the capacity to actually do the right things - we only have the capacity to report. (CSO3)

This sense of disillusionment was widespread. Every CSO emphasized the overwhelming time burden, as CSO1 put it: "that 90% of the time has to be spent just on reporting - that's not value-creating". In addition to making sustainability work more procedural rather than value-creating, several mentioned that they had already hired, or were planning to hire, dedicated staff just to manage CSRD reporting (CSO2; CSO3), while another raised concerns about the cost of mandatory auditing: "We're talking about the million-kroner range," noted CSO1.

The issue was not just the scale of resources involved, but the lack of clear return. As CSO1 noted, "At that point, you should really start seeing... you should also be seeing some results." Instead, the emphasis on quantification and documentation led some to feel increasingly disconnected from the substance of sustainability work. CSO6 expressed this uncertainty candidly:

Even though I took it on, I did feel this question: *'Is this really my big issue?'* As a Head of Sustainability, I have strong values when it comes to sustainability and the real estate sector, so I wondered—will this actually... Are we really going to do things better? Will this help us find better solutions and make better plans? And I'm still unsure about that. I have to admit, I'm still very uncertain. (CSO6)

⁵This experience of disconnection will be elaborated on in Part 2.

⁶The phrase "*møllers-tran*" (cod liver oil) is used metaphorically here. It suggests that while something is good for you in principle, it may have been administered in too large a dose—making the experience unpleasant or excessive.

What emerges here is a picture of valuation under strain. While double materiality was intended as a way to make sustainability matter - to prioritize what is most relevant and impactful - it is also experienced by many as a "bureaucratic machine" (CSO5) that consumes time and energy without obvious return. The gap between ambition and application is not just about capacity, but about meaning: whether the CSRD ultimately strengthens sustainability work, or obscures it beneath a layer of formalized routines. This raises a deeper question: what happens in the process of rendering sustainability legible? How do the actors and practices it travels through engage with it - and how are they, in turn, shaped by their encounters?

In sum, while the idea of double materiality was rarely contested, the practical realities of implementing it point to significant tensions that we will continue to explore. These included time and resource constraints, ambiguity around definitions, and difficulties aligning sustainability expertise with financial reporting structures. These frictions underscore how valuation is not just a technical exercise, but a site of negotiation between professional worlds, expectations, and forms of expertise. It is to these sites of negotiation that we now begin to turn. For sustainability information to be created, data must first be gathered. This process begins only after the CSRD is translated into the local contexts of companies. It is within these organizational settings that new mobilizations and translations occur - with CSOs playing a central role in navigating, interpreting, and enacting the directive on the ground.

4.1.3 Circulating Sustainability: CSOs as Translators, Sense-Makers and Negotiators

The tensions described so far, do not resolve themselves. Rather, they are taken up and worked through by those tasked with turning these regulatory ideals into practice. Positioned at the intersection of the external demands and internal structures, CSOs navigate the shifting terrain of the CSRD from within their organizations. The CSOs I spoke with represent a diverse range of professional backgrounds: some trained as engineers, others as economists, and many occupy positions that bridge technical and managerial expertise. What connects them is their function as translators. This process involves linking the external requirements of the CSRD with internal mobilizations, translating sustainability across departments, outward to auditors, and inward into the report itself.

The first step in this *chain of translation* (Latour, 1990), however, begins with how the CSOs themselves come to understand the directive. As CSO2 put it, "I'm a civil engineer by training, so I'm not used to reading those long EU documents written in that kind of language." This sentiment was widely shared, regardless of background: many described the scale and language of the EU documents as difficult to engage with directly. This might be a reason why, for most companies, the CSRD is not made legible through the directive documents themselves, but through translations given by other professional - particularly auditors - who translate regulatory texts into actionable procedures. Initiatives like the Sustainability Academy hosted by the Norwegian Auditor's Association often serve as the first point of engagement with the CSRD's demands. Resulting in auditors more-often-not serving as the first link in the CSRD's chain of translations. Reflecting on their participation in the Sustainability Academy's CSRD

introduction program, CSO9 described the experience as follows:

“So, we took part in this six-day training program, where the auditors ran through 300 PowerPoint slides per day. Their approach is very rigid—they have a strict, rules-based mindset.”

The EU documents themselves were difficult to make sense of - and so too were the approaches taken by the first links in the chain of translation. As CSO11 states, understanding the directive was especially challenging because of "how it's structured in an auditor-like way." This highlights an important point: rather than reducing uncertainty, the translations offered by auditors often failed to clarify things for CSOs. This is heightened by, as CSO2 reflects on, as they think back to the beginning of the CSRD process, "I don't think either the auditor or we were fully ready at that point." Auditors - who are themselves still interpreting and making sense of the evolving framework (CSO2; CSO3; CSO5) - are positioned as the source of understanding this process. This brings us to a central point: for many CSOs, reporting under the CSRD feels like the blind leading the blind. While materiality assessments are meant to establish the perspective through which sustainability should be reported, the question of *how* this should be done - and *what* should be included - remains open and uncertain. This uncertainty reflects a shared experience described by several of the CSOs interviewed - being the translator between the CSRD and their company. As CSO7 put it: "We didn't have a chance to fully understand the requirements of the CSRD" before having to bring it back into the organization. Sense-making, therefore, is not a preliminary step; it is an ongoing, iterative process that unfolds throughout the CSRD's implementation.

Even as CSOs work to interpret the structure and requirements of the directive, they must simultaneously begin translating these expectations into internal action- mobilizing data collection and coordinating operational responses. With no clear practices yet established, companies are left grappling with two fundamental questions: *How do we operationalize the CSRD?* and *How do we make it applicable and useful in our specific context?* What emerges is a fragmented and recursive chain of interpretation, where each actor must make assumptions, fill in knowledge gaps, and hope that their choices will ultimately align with what auditors deem acceptable. But sense-making alone does not suffice. CSOs must also move quickly to organize implementation - setting up working groups, creating workflows across departments, and determining what data is needed and who is responsible for gathering it. The following sections follow this process more closely, showing how CSOs move from interpretation to implementation - organizing people, processes, and information flows in an effort to bring the CSRD to life within their organizations.

Through this tracing, we come to see that the CSRD has not been experienced uniformly. For some, it has added layers of complexity and frustration. For others, it has served as an energizing force. Most clearly expressed by CSO9: "Suddenly you had the Chief Financial Officer involved, the finance department engaged - that gave the whole effort a completely different kind of momentum."

Yet while the involvement of finance brings momentum, at least in the eyes of CSO9, the

actual process of collaboration often remains fragmented. In many companies, the division of labor follows a functional split: technical teams are tasked with identifying “the key metrics related to the issues we have determined to be materially significant” (CSO9), while the finance department assumes formal responsibility for producing the report. As CSO5 put it, “We’re just content providers, but it does feel like... well, it’s not just our finance department, you know, but also heavily supported by our auditors, who want everything to be extremely schematic.” In this model, sustainability specialists provide the substance, while finance and audit-oriented teams translate it into a formal report. This configuration makes sense within the CSRD’s logic: the sustainability report is to be written in the language of financial reporting, cross-referenced with financial disclosures, and published as part of the same reporting package (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 77). But for some informants, it also carried strategic weight: assigning formal ownership of the report to the CFO was seen as a way to protect sustainability from becoming “*just a reporting practice*” (CSO3), potentially freeing up time to focus on more substantive sustainability work beyond reporting itself.

Regardless, the CSOs remained responsible for mobilizing the broader organization to gather the necessary information. Because the required sustainability information is spread across multiple departments, simplifying and adapting the technical frameworks of the CSRD became a crucial part of the work. This often meant drawing on expertise from people in unrelated roles, and translating the regulatory language into something accessible across the company. As CSO8 explained, “We had to pull people from completely unrelated roles to handle sustainability reporting, and they struggled to understand the requirements.” Similarly, CSO7 noted, “It’s heavy material, so we’re also trying to simplify it for the organization,” emphasizing the need to make the reporting manageable for those outside the sustainability department. Without such simplification, CSO1, half-laughing, warned that “they [the other workers] will simply die.”

Some CSOs reflected on how their own backgrounds shaped their ability to manage this internal transition work. CSO9, for instance, noted that having “a very hands-on background from working in the construction industry in various places” gave them a practical understanding of “what’s actually being reported and why,” which proved especially valuable when employees seemed “unsure about the purpose of the reporting” (CSO9). Likewise, CSO7 stressed that while many employees have “a lot of knowledge - sometimes more than they realize,” it is important to help them understand “why they are providing data” and “why reporting matters,” without overwhelming them with “all the technicalities of every ESRS requirement.” The specific data to be provided depends on what sustainability topics come to be deemed material, but the requirements can be wide-ranging - from energy consumption by source, to employee turnover rates broken down by age and gender, or the existence of whistleblower mechanisms (EFRAG IG 3, 2024). In some cases, the required data can be far more detailed: examples include potentially stranded assets due to transition risks (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS E1-9, AR. 73 a), the number of workplace incidents linked to severe human rights violations, or the total amount paid in fines, penalties, and related costs (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS S1-17, 103 c). Through these everyday acts of simplification, coordination, and explanation, CSOs functioned as important intermediaries, translating the

CSRD into organizational contexts that were often not fully prepared for its complexity. They made the regulation operable by making it more accessible so that the broader organization can partake in acting upon it.

At the same time as CSOs were working to understand the CSRD and find ways of translating its complex requirements into simplified, actionable forms, they also faced the parallel task of mobilizing internal actors to support the emerging reporting processes. Organizational responses varied. Some companies created new cross-functional teams, while others maintained their existing departmental structures. Confronted with what CSO7 described as an "overwhelming demand for information," companies adopted different tactics to align their internal resources with the reporting requirements. One tactic was to establish common ground through joint training initiatives. For example, CSO6 sent "one from finance and one from sustainability" to the Sustainability Academy run by the Auditor's Association, aiming to build a team capable of bridging domains. This approach reflected an attempt to entangle expertise, promote cross-departmental collaboration, and build shared understanding across professional boundaries.

Other companies chose to maintain a more siloed structure, assigning reporting responsibilities along existing departmental lines. As CSO2 explained: "If something falls under HR, then their internal team handles it." Similarly, CSO5 described a model where:

The main responsibility lies with the corporate finance and accounting teams. The environmental side falls under our sustainability department, while the social aspects - including the Transparency Act and everything that comes with it - are handled by HR.

These differing organizational strategies highlight how the translation of the CSRD is not only a matter of interpreting regulatory content, but also how companies choose to distribute responsibility, build capacity, and align their systems with external demands. In other words, the CSRD has not just influenced how companies report or approach sustainability - it has also, in some cases, reshaped internal structures and decision-making processes to better align with its logic. Company size appeared to play a significant role in shaping these choices. Larger firms - such as those represented by CSO4 and CSO5 - typically had the resources to maintain dedicated sustainability, finance, and HR departments, enabling more specialized yet coordinated reporting structures. In contrast, smaller companies, while still large enough to maintain separate departments, often relied on just one or two individuals per function. This leaner setup facilitated tighter communication and more fluid information-sharing. In such settings, sustainability personnel could more easily draw on colleagues across departments, which helped ease the burden of the CSRD's broad data requirements and reduce the feeling of being overwhelmed.

Size also mattered in terms of geography. Several companies reported having operations spread across different regions of Norway. While decentralization was not always an obstacle to collecting sustainability data, it could introduce other challenges - particularly when combined with the technical complexity of the reporting templates and their reliance

on English. A crucial part of the internal translation work involved engaging subsidiaries - that is, smaller companies within the larger corporate group - in the reporting process. However, subsidiaries varied widely in their degree of autonomy, and some operated without a centralized HR system or corporate governance framework to facilitate coordination. As CSO6 put it, "Coordinating this process is like solving a complex puzzle." Language barriers added an additional layer of complexity. Language barriers added yet another layer of difficulty. CSO1 noted that several subsidiaries were located in Northern Norway, where some offices had less than five employees. These local teams often had no prior experience with ESG reporting and, in many cases, had limited English proficiency. Given that "everything is in English, and all the templates are in English," the task of translating the technical content became formidable - not just in terms of sense-making, but also quite simply, in reading it.

Mobilizing across the company did not just involve organizing teams to gather data - it also required figuring out how to gather the data in the first place. Companies, as a result, found themselves starting from vastly different baselines. Broadly speaking, there were three main approaches: fully manual data collection; relying on whatever existing systems happened to be available; or a more experimental approach. For many CSOs, data quality and accessibility remained persistent challenges. Still, there was a degree of cautious optimism: as more companies are pushed into the reporting process, the hope is that initial chaos will eventually give way to greater sustainability information across companies which might someday be tracked with something resembling precision (CSO4; CSO5; CSO9). This reflects an investment in the broader project of harmonization embedded in the CSRD: the vision that by making sustainability data and information uniform, and enabling its circulation across organizations, sectors, and countries, a more cohesive and interoperable system of sustainability information can emerge - one that allows for a freer flow of useful data.

However, as we continue tracing this process, we will see that harmonization in practice more closely resembles Laurent's (2022) description - where the pursuit of disentanglement and objectivity results in displacement. That is, while information is flattened to enable circulation across new domains, and thereby opens up for greater coordination at a distance. The cost is detaching knowledge from its original context and meaning. In this case, rather than simply increasing the flow and cohesion of sustainability information, harmonization also entails this form of flattening - one that many CSOs are directly involved in managing. The information that comes to circulate is not shaped by situated sustainability concerns or local priorities, but by what can be abstracted from context and made to fit within institutional formats and technical systems. As we will come to see, CSOs often find themselves translating complex, locally embedded sustainability issues into standardized categories - not because these categories capture the full meaning of the CSOs contexts, but because they are what the reporting system recognizes as valid.

This theme of displacement will continue to follow us, as we return later to the process of flattening in more detail. But already at the stage of data gathering, frictions begin to emerge. In companies without established systems, even identifying the relevant data was a demanding task. This manual process typically involved locating individuals who might possess key

information - such as data on completed building projects - requesting it (often via email), manually organizing it into Excel spreadsheets, and eventually compiling the report in Word documents (CSO2; CSO10). A major challenge was simply figuring out who had access to which pieces of information for each of the CSRD's many data points - a scavenger hunt that usually started with a project director and then spiraled outward to project managers, site managers, procurement officers, cost estimators, or payroll staff (CSO10). Without systems to automate the process, companies relied on unstructured, ad hoc methods that frequently triggered "urgent, last-minute requests" like "Can you figure this out by the end of the day?" (CSO10). This process created friction, particularly for those who had yet to establish systems for more systematic data gathering. As CO10 put it bluntly: "It's a nightmare. There's just so much manual searching - looking up numbers for energy providers, figuring out how much power we've saved... It's exhausting." Even before data can be translated, flattened, or reported, it must first be located, extracted, and reorganized - a task that, for many, already constitutes an intense and time-consuming form of everyday labor. This early step, often taken for granted in more abstract accounts of reporting, makes visible just how much work is required to render sustainability legible in the first place.

By contrast, some companies had existing systems that aligned more naturally with the CSRD's demands - significantly reducing the initial labor required to locate and assemble data, and easing the early stages of translation. These systems had already been designed to produce centralized oversight and abstract environmental performance from ongoing operations, essentially displacing sustainability data in ways that made it more readily circulatable for internal strategy-making. As CSO3 put it, "We calculate climate budgets for everything we do. Compared to our industry peers, we have a solid foundation," noting that even major projects "include climate budgeting early on" and that they also have "circular economy targets, like reuse in landscapes, outdoor areas, and buildings" (CSO3). Rather than relying on internal measurements, these companies often partnered with third-party networks to source their emissions and waste data - drawing from suppliers like Norsk Gjenvinning (Norwegian Recycling), Franzefoss, or Energynett (CSO3; CSO5; CSO9). Notably, the CSO from the only company interviewed without a dedicated sustainability team described a particularly decentralized approach to data gathering. Their process relied on an ongoing project monitoring system, where project managers recorded progress as projects unfolded - tracking materials used, suppliers, and quantities - which made sustainability metrics easier to compile (CSO8).

Some were even experimenting with more ambitious forms of integration. One CSO described efforts to link invoices to climate impact data, attempting to automate the connection between procurement and sustainability reporting (CSO9). For now, the system relies on NACE codes, assigning CO emissions per monetary unit spent - a method that, as the CSO acknowledged "represents the lowest tier of data quality," although they expressed optimism that improvements "seem very cool." For some, then, the work of linking disparate data sources - however experimental - was not only a technical task, but also a space for curiosity, innovation, and even enjoyment.

The experiences described in this section illustrate how CSOs act as internal mobilizers, translators, and, at times, infrastructural improvisers - adapting not only their own practices, but often reshaping organizational workflows to meet the demands of the CSRD. From scavenger hunts for fragmented data to pre-existing systems that facilitate circulation, we've seen how the process of rendering sustainability legible is both uneven and labor-intensive - frequently producing friction before data even reaches the point of being flattened or formalized.

So far, these mobilization efforts have focused inward: building cross-departmental teams, patching together data systems, and experimenting with new ways of linking financial and environmental metrics. However, the CSRD also calls for a second, more formalized kind of mobilization: the engagement of stakeholders. In the following section, I turn to this outward- and inward-facing dimension of the directive - where companies are asked to identify, consult, and integrate the perspectives of those potentially affected by their activities.

4.1.3.1 Stakeholder Engagement: From Top-Down to Bottom-Up - and Back Again

As sustainability data begins its transformation into sustainability information to fit within the final report, it becomes clear that this process involves more than simply gathering inputs: it begins to reveal deeper tensions around harmonization and displacement. These tensions continue in the next phase of the reporting process, where input must be gathered not only from within the company, but also from outside it. This section examines how CSOs engage stakeholders and how their input is filtered, reformulated, or sidelined in the reporting process. Under the CSRD, stakeholder engagement is a method for gathering input into materiality assessment, helping to identify the topics that should undergo further assessment. Stakeholders are defined broadly as individuals or groups who can affect or be affected by a company's activities, either directly or through its value chain (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.1). By tracing how stakeholder input is incorporated - or left out - this section shows that decisions about what to include are shaped not just by relevance, but also by organizational priorities. While stakeholder engagement is meant to bring in diverse perspectives, these inputs are filtered through internal valuation processes - where engagement may be seen as valuable in itself, or reshaped to align with what the organization already considers important.

The ESRS introduces a bifurcation between two categories of stakeholders: affected stakeholders, whose interests are impacted by the company's activities, and *users of sustainability statements*, such as investors, lenders, business partners, civil society organizations, and public authorities (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.1). While both groups are recognized, the directive tells companies to place particular emphasis on affected stakeholders as a key input for assessing actual and potential impacts. Companies are expected to engage a broad range of actors - from employees and suppliers to local communities and, optionally, nature itself as a "silent stakeholder", through the inclusion of biological assessments (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 6-7). Sustainability reporting is therefore supposed to be not simply disclosing facts, but a process shaped by dialogue. At the same time, how much influence stakeholders actually have over the final report, and which stakeholders are identified as important to in-

clude, is largely up to the company. While companies must describe how stakeholder interests are taken into account - especially in relation to developing business strategies and models - there is still significant discretion in how this input is handled and whether it leads to actions (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 2, §3, SBM-2, paras. 43–45). Through this, the CSRD attempts to transform sustainability as a form of participatory knowledge-making. Yet, this formal obligation to engage with stakeholders coexists with considerable flexibility in how their voices are ultimately used - or not.

The description that follows is based primarily on an internal document provided by an informant, detailing how their company approached the stakeholder engagement process under the CSRD. As discussed in the methods chapter, this document is supplemented by interview data that helps contextualize and verify the account. The company in question is a smaller organization with a relatively strong sustainability team, characterized by substantial resources and staffing. While this provides a useful example of a structured approach, later sections will also examine how stakeholder engagement unfolds in other companies, where the processes involve more substantial filtering and reinterpretation of input.

Through the process detailed in the internal document, the organization identified two main groups of stakeholders. The affected stakeholders included project collaborators, operational partners (such as cafeteria service providers), employees, neighboring communities, renters, the board of directors and property owners. Users of sustainability statements included banks, media outlets, insurance companies, and industry associations (Internal Document, 2024).

After identifying relevant stakeholders, the next step involved active engagement, typically through interviews or roundtable discussions (Internal Document, 2024). These interactions were used to develop a long list of potentially material sustainability issues. In one case, the stakeholder engagement process resulted in 27 identified topics, spanning areas such as corruption, human rights violations, renewable energy, and waste management. These topics were selected as relevant through discussions structured around the sustainability topics, sub-topics, and sub-subtopics listed in the ESRS.

To further refine this list, the company conducted a survey distributed to all employees, aiming to assess which issues were considered most material from an internal perspective. Employees were asked to evaluate each of the 27 topics based on four questions:

- How serious or significant would the impact be if we did not focus on this issue?
- How likely or widespread is it that this issue might occur?
- How much influence or control does the company have over this issue?
- Would this issue result in long-term or irreversible environmental impacts?

(Internal Document, 2024).

The survey results were subsequently categorized into an A-list and a B-list, based on how material the respondents - representing 89 percent of the company's employees - perceived each topic to be. These prioritized lists were then brought back into further workshops

and roundtable discussions involving both internal and external stakeholders. During these sessions, participants worked to link the identified sustainability risks to specific financial thresholds. According to the internal methodology, risks estimated to have a financial impact of 0-12 million NOK were classified as low, 12-30 million as medium, and over 30 million as high (Internal Document, 2024). In line with the design of materiality as a device, these thresholds were not predefined, but constructed by the actors conducting the assessments themselves. The finalized assessments were intended to feed into broader corporate processes, including strategy development, action plans, risk management, and sustainability reporting (Internal Document, 2024). This translation of stakeholder concerns into financial risk thresholds exemplifies how valuation devices mediate what counts as "material." Through stakeholder engagement, the selection of company-specific thresholds, and the translation of, often qualitative, concerns into estimated financial impacts, sustainability issues are not merely identified - they are actively shaped and prioritized. The entanglement between materiality, risks, opportunities, and monetary valuation processes will be elaborated on in the next section.

The process described above comes from a smaller company that was invested heavily in building a resource-strong sustainability procedure. This team plays a central role in determining who is engaged, how stakeholder input is interpreted, and which sustainability concerns are ultimately prioritized. Notably, the CSRD does not prescribe fixed procedures for stakeholder engagement, leaving substantial discretionary space for companies to filter and reframe input according to internal priorities and valuation processes. In this example, the company's prioritization flowed primarily from environmental concerns, which were then linked to financial thresholds. In other cases, however, the structure was less organized, with financial considerations taking precedence from the outset.

Stakeholder engagement under the CSRD can be seen as an attempt at a form of democratic reconfiguration, where local knowledge is brought into consideration. These processes seek to open up dialogical spaces in which climate and sustainability knowledge and action is meant to be co-produced with affected actors. In principle, this includes a wide range of stakeholders - such as tenants, local communities, and Indigenous groups - who may be directly or indirectly impacted by corporate activities, such as biodiversity loss or pollution (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 2, SBM-2, DR. S3-2). In practice, however, the material suggest a more selective engagement. Stakeholders with institutional power - such as banks, investors, and business partners - received more priority, while affected communities were not represented. Since companies can choose who counts as a relevant stakeholder, how they are engaged, and how their input is weighted, the democratic potential of this form of engagement, has not yet been realized.

Still, for some CSOs, stakeholder engagement was seen as an opportunity. This was especially the case for CSO7 who viewed the process as a highly valuable practice; going so far as to construct expert groups across departmental structures that will be able to consult on specific issues. Yet even in such proactive cases, the analysis suggests that stakeholder input is not incorporated on its own terms. Rather, it is shaped by internal valuation logics and structuring devices embedded in the CSRD - logics that often narrow the space for contestation and

diminish the influence of less institutionalized stakeholders..

Most of these challenges in this process arose when departments or subsidiaries overestimated the weight of their own concerns and opinions. While their input may have reflected real and legitimate issues, these concerns did not always align with the priorities of the broader organization. In effect, what was meaningful at the local level could be rendered immaterial at the corporate level. As CSO1 explained: "Some small companies assessed issues as highly material, but in the broader corporate context, they weren't." Similarly, CSO2 noted that "a key challenge was determining whether identified risks were actually significant, or if they were just perceived as such" (CSO2). This dynamic highlights how materiality assessments are continuously shaped by internal valuation practices, as different departments or subsidiaries seek to elevate the importance of their issues within the reporting process, or just to, in their mind objectively, state the issues they are facing. CSO2 goes on to say:

When HR participated, they naturally focused heavily on employee-related issues, which they consider highly material. (...) As a result scoring was largely based on subjective opinions rather than a standardized approach. We have since had to go through multiple rounds to re-evaluate and adjust the assigned values.

To address these tensions, central sustainability teams often applied structured filtering mechanisms to ensure that only inputs deemed significant in the broader corporate context were included. As explained by CSO1 "it is clear that what is most material for [company name] has been the overarching focus. This applies to revenue, financial results, impacts, risks, and opportunities." The role of translating inputs through risks and opportunities and into financial valuations is the topic of part 2. What is important here, is that even when subsidiaries or departments contributed to defining materiality, their assessments were not necessarily final. Corporate leadership frequently reinterpreted, adjusted, or reclassified certain issues to align with auditor expectations or strategic priorities. As CSO1 explained: "Now, we have had to make some top-down adjustments - both to the companies' assessments and to the final consolidated assessment." This shows another side of CSOs function: they do not merely transmit information up and down the organization - they actively filter, reinterpret, and reshape it. Their role is to ensure that materiality assessments remain internally coherent, externally defensible, and strategically aligned. What those valuation processes ultimately emphasize - whether sustainability goals, risk exposure, or potential financial results - is often left to the discretion of the CSO, the reporting lead (such as the CFO), and their negotiations with auditors or the board.

As the examples from CSO1 and CSO2 illustrate, topics raised by departments or stakeholders may be deprioritized in favor of issues that carry greater evaluative weight within the organization. For instance, concerns raised by HR representatives may reflect genuine workplace challenges, but if they do not translate to metrics like absenteeism or retention - factors with clearer financial implications - they may be filtered out during the assessment process. The CSO may seek to faithfully represent stakeholder perspectives, but once this input passes through multiple layers of internal review, formatting, and prioritization, its original meaning can be reshaped - or lost altogether. While the CSRD promotes a double materiality

framework intended to balance financial and impact perspectives, this balance can easily be tilted toward corporate priorities. This is not necessarily due to bad faith, but a consequence of structure. Auditors, CSOs, and internal reporting systems act as obligatory passage points - channels through which all information must pass, and where judgments about relevance are made (Callon, 1984). In practice, this means that only knowledge which can be made legible within reporting systems move forward.

With internal mobilizations now generating inputs through data gathering and stakeholder engagement, a new stage of translation begins. These inputs must next be assessed not just for their descriptive value, but for their implications: framed as risks, opportunities, and potential financial impacts. As we will see, this phase introduces new levels of abstraction and assumption - marking a shift from collecting sustainability data to forecasting how it might affect the company's future. This marks a new phase in the translation chain: one where sustainability concerns are recast as risks to be mitigated or opportunities to be seized.

4.2 The Tension Between Assumptions and Rigidity

While the processes of data gathering and stakeholder engagement are designed to surface what matters, they do not settle the question of how sustainability concerns should be understood or represented. As we move into the next stage of the CSRD's implementation, inputs collected through internal mobilization must now be assessed, modeled, and rendered legible - translated into forms such as risks, opportunities, and projected impacts. This phase shifts attention from the descriptive to the anticipatory, asking companies not only to account for current conditions, but to evaluate how environmental and social concerns may evolve, and how they might affect the company's future financial performance. In other words, it sets in motion a broader transformation: sustainability work increasingly becomes a matter of translating imagined futures into auditable facts. Through these expectations, professional judgment remains important - but for many CSOs, the new ways of valuing sustainability make the exercise of judgment feel less like applying their situated knowledge, and more adapting to an externally imposed framework (CSO8).

4.2.1 Rendering the Future Accountable: Impacts, Risks, and Opportunities

Having established the centrality of stakeholder engagement, internal mobilization, and the labor involved in gathering sustainability inputs, we now turn to how these inputs are evaluated and prioritized. This is where the Impacts, Risks, and Opportunities (IRO) framework becomes essential: it provides the structure through which companies are expected to assess the significance of sustainability issues - not only in terms of their societal or environmental effects, but also their potential financial consequences. Under the CSRD, companies are expected to conduct a comprehensive analysis of their activities, value chains, and stakeholders to identify both vulnerabilities to loss and openings for gain (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 2, DR. IRO-1). As CSO8 summarized, the process required "analyzing everything from every angle - a full 360-degree evaluation." Crucially, an IRO assessment extends beyond mapping the present: companies must anticipate how sustainability risks and opportunities might evolve over time and integrate these projections into management strategies and disclosures. According to the ESRS, risks often arise from dependencies on natural or social resources and are considered financially material if they are expected to increase costs, reduce income, or negatively affect intangible resources such as reputation (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, §3.3.38; ESRS 1, §3.5.49-50) - another example of how, as Fourcade (2016) shows, even intangible aspects such as reputation are pulled into financial calculations, made visible through their anticipated monetary consequences. Opportunities, by contrast, refer to factors that could strengthen income, reduce costs, or enhance unrecognized forms of capital (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 14(b)). 4.3 illustrates how sustainability impacts, risks, and opportunities are connected within the CSRD framework. Companies are expected to map how external sustainability factors - such as climate change and social risks - influence their business models, strategies, and key financial metrics like operating costs (OPEX) and investment expenses (CAPEX). This analysis feeds directly into the materiality assessment, where companies determine which risks and opportunities are significant enough to report.

In short, the figure shows how sustainability concerns must be traced all the way from their external impacts to their anticipated financial consequences, ultimately shaping what becomes visible in the sustainability report.

Figure 4.3: (EFRAG, 2024b)

Building on this modification of the issue at hand, after identifying risks and opportunities, companies must determine which are "material for reporting" (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 15). This decision is deeply tied to forward-looking calculations about financial impacts. According to the CSRD, material risks and opportunities should normally be assessed based on their likelihood of occurrence. However, if the potential consequences are significant enough, even low-likelihood events must still be considered material (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 15). This approach shifts the focus of valuation toward the anticipated impact on future cash flows or value of other resources (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 14). In this way, valuation becomes a future-oriented practice: a means of "future-proofing" the company by rendering uncertain, non-actualized futures calculable. Importantly, the assessment is not limited to conventional financial capital. It also covers capitals not traditionally recognized in accounting frameworks - such as natural, human, and social resources. Issues of clean air, ecosystem integrity, employee retention and reputational standing are drawn into the space of financial relevance because they can influence a company's ability to secure the resources it needs for business procedures - or affect the quality, pricing, or reliability of the relationships, suppliers, customers, regulators, it depends on (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 14; §3.5.50).

Having outlined how IROs frame sustainability through future-oriented financial calculations, it is important to situate these developments within broader transformations in valuation practices. As Chiapello 2016 shows in her analysis of the IFRS, calculative practices have increasingly come to be "ruled" by financial techniques and logics: decision-making tools are restructured to align with financial models and market-oriented assumptions. Although these techniques present themselves as neutral, they tend to privilege the interest of capital providers. Through such practices, companies are evaluated not primarily as producers - whether of goods and services as in Chiapello's case, or of improved sustainability outcomes, as in the case here - but instead as collections of future assets and risks - like tradable packages whose value depends on how well they are expected to perform financially. This shift in perspective, from focusing on present activities to forecasting future gains or losses, refocuses the issue from immediate action to speculative positioning. We can recognize these dynamics at work in how the CSRD frames IRO assessments: relying on probabilistic models and scenario analyses to estimate risks and opportunities, much like financial markets predict fluctuations in asset value. In this way, the construction of sustainability as something calculable and governable rests on deploying of valuation devices that frame potential futures within specific financial and regulatory logics - translating sustainability into forms legible to investors.

For CSO4, the idea of IROs appeared relatively straightforward. They described it in terms of "changing demand(s) due to commitments to emissions reduction targets and risks", highlighting that the conditions the company operates under - laws, market demands, political pressures - are constantly shifting. This made questions like "how well is the company prepared for a 2030-2050 low-emission future" central to company strategy. CSO4 further distilled the task at hand to a relatively basic question: "Does our company belong in the future we see today - or the one that's still taking shape?". For this finance-oriented CSO, IROs became a natural extension of familiar practices of risk assessment and market positioning. If there is little regulatory or market pressure for costly sustainable solutions, being the first mover could place a company at a "market disadvantage." In this sense, IROs serve as a valuable tool for navigating an uncertain future, helping companies meet - but not exceed - what is expected. Perhaps it is through experience in the financial field that viewing a company, and its relationship to sustainability, as a matter of strategic forecasting came more naturally.

For others, however, valuing sustainability through risks and opportunities proved more challenging. CSO10, when asked to explain IROs, reflected that it was difficult to grasp the idea: "We have to construct our buildings in a way that accounts for climate changes. That's a risk, I'd say". When prompted about opportunities, they hesitated, eventually suggesting vaguely "Something in the social aspect?" before admitting, "Honestly, that's a hard question to answer". Their difficulty in articulating opportunities hints at the broader challenge some CSOs face when asked to translate complex sustainability concerns into the language of financial futures. The struggles observed among many CSOs in translating IROs - and, more broadly, double materiality - reflect more than a lack of familiarity with the concepts; they signal a tension in adapting to how the issue of sustainability itself is being modified. Sustainability risks are no longer framed primarily as environmental or social harms, but increasingly as potential future financial impacts - a shift central to the CSRD's approach to assessing risks and opportunities.

This entanglement between sustainability concerns and financial valuation processes is not new. As Asdal & Engen show (2024), the category of "climate risk" was developed and consolidated through the work of the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD), which reframed climate change from an environmental concern into a potential financial risk for companies. This shift is part of what they call the "climate-finance nexus," where the consequences of climate policies - originally aimed at reducing harm - are increasingly interpreted as so-called *transition risks* for companies. The CSRD builds directly on this double conception of sustainability-related risk: distinguishing between physical risks, such as climate disasters, biodiversity loss, and resource deletions, and financial transition risks arising from changes in policy or markets (e.g., stricter emissions regulations or declining demand for carbon-intensive products) (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 47), (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS 1, App. A, AR. 12(d)). These categories do not merely capture immediate environmental impacts; they foreground anticipated financial effects tied to broader societal transformations. In this way, climate risk - and sustainability risk more broadly - is reframed: no longer understood primarily as harm to ecosystems or communities, but increasingly as potential disruptions to economic stability, asset valuation, and investor confidence (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 9; 14).

This modification of sustainability within the logics of financial resilience and competitive viability demands more than new calculations - it requires a fundamental shift in how sustainability itself is understood and valued. Sustainability is not integrated by transforming financial evaluation systems, but by adapting sustainability concerns to fit into existing financial logics, where relevance is framed through calculative practices of potential gains and losses. For many CSOs this translation is deeply challenging. As CSO6 reflected, "The hardest part will be linking human impact to financial consequences. We haven't done that yet, but I think it will be the most difficult task." Their comment captures a broader struggle: even as environmental and social harms are pulled into financial calculations, making these connections in credible, defensible ways remains a fraught and uncertain. Some links between human and financial consequences are familiar such as the cost of sick leave for the state. But connecting broader impacts, like worker well-being or harms to the local communities, into quantifiable financial terms might feel forced, artificial, or deeply speculative. As financial valuation devices began to reshape sustainability work, many CSOs felt increasingly disconnected from the more hands-on practices they were used to.

4.2.1.1 From Operations to Speculation

Before turning to how CSOs engaged with applying IRO assessments, it is important to foreground a recurring theme across the interviews: a growing sense of disconnection - not merely from specific tasks, but from the foundations of sustainability work as most CSOs had previously practiced it. This disconnection took multiple forms: the flattening of tangible, experience-based practices into abstract financial valuations; the tension between professional expertise and externally imposed reporting structures; and a widening gap between the CSRD's promises and its perceived outcomes. It was, in other words, a disconnection between doing and reporting, between acting in the present and accounting for imagined futures.

Notably, this was not rooted in resistance to regulation - most CSOs were already familiar with working under sustainability frameworks. Instead, it reflected a deeper transformation in how sustainability is being redefined under the CSRD: moving away from grounded, context-specific interventions and toward the speculative logics of financial risk and opportunity. As I will show in the next section, these tensions became particularly visible in how CSOs navigated the process of IRO assessments.

In conversations with their advisor, CSO8 reflects on the process of valuing potential future scenarios; "Yeah, because a lot of it felt like: *"What if...?" "Do you think...?" "Could this be the case...?"* Like, yes, anything *could* happen." At this point, a noticeable sense of disconnection began to surface - not just from specific tasks, but from the core practice of how sustainability had previously been understood and enacted. As CSO2 pointed out, the wide variation in outcomes across similar companies "shows that there are a lot of subjective opinions involved," while CSO10 described working with these calculations as dealing with "fictive numbers," losing the sense that they were working with something tangible, "the outcomes aren't real anyway". For many CSOs, the shift from working with concrete, observable impacts to navigating abstract, speculative risk models disrupted their connection to what they felt was real, grounded, and actionable. This disconnection is perhaps a natural reaction to the structural shift brought about by the CSRD. Before its introduction, many CSOs has worked closely with building projects, direct environmental interventions, and operational systems - forms of sustainability work that were tangible, material, and rooted in the present. In contrast, the CSRD demands that they engage with hypothetical futures, complex financial modeling, and scenario-based forecasting, paired within a rigid and standardized reporting structure. What is being disconnected, then, is the relationship between doing and reporting - between hands-on sustainability practice and the abstract, decontextualized logic of audit-ready reporting. This disconnect was reported across the board - even by CSOs without technical backgrounds - with the notable exception of the CSO who came from a financial background. Their familiarity with financial modeling and valuations seemed to ease the transition. For the others, the shift that Chiapello (2016) describes: companies transforming from producing tangible to producing information - specifically, information about financial viability.

In addition to the disconnection caused by this shift in perspective another source of disconnection emerges from the growing role of and time required for interpretation. The professional judgment demanded by IROs and materiality assessments increasingly felt more like speculation. As CSO6 reflected, "what's the financial consequence of climate change? If we get floods or extreme weather, how will it affect our buildings, materials, etc.? It's hard to quantify." Understanding what goes into this should be included in these estimates - especially when operating within a perspective borrowed from finance - only deepened the uncertainty. CSO5 expanded on this challenge, describing interpretations as the "tricky part," and characterizing some of the framework's prescribed distinctions as bordering on the absurd: "What's the difference between a short-sleeve and a long-sleeve sweater in this context? What is "good enough"? How significant is "significant"? It's hard to pin down." They went on to reflect on how this ambiguity shaped their everyday work: "They dictate the framework, and

we sit through endless meetings trying to interpret what we need to report on."

The findings from my interviews closely mirror Cool's (2019) study of how researchers grappled with the application of the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Although GDPR aims to promote transparency and accountability, Cool shows how its broad and flexible language often left researchers unsure about how to comply in practice. Despite legal texts being available, many described the law as "unknowable", forcing them to guess what was required. Cool ultimately argues that broad accountability principles, while intended to encourage responsible behavior, shift ethical and legal burdens onto individuals, creating unintended dilemmas and forms of "accountability anxiety." A similar pattern is present in my findings: CSOs describe the extensive time needed to cross-disciplinary discussions of each ESRS, confusion about the scope of reporting requirements, and difficulties navigating the overwhelming volume of legal documents. Yet perhaps instead of experiencing accountability anxiety, it was more a form of accountability resignation. Across interviews, CSOs consistently voiced that they were trying to do the right thing - not to avoid responsibility, but to meet expectations within the limits of time, capacity, and clarity (CSO2; CSO3; CSO6). But the process displace concrete sustainability work, and uncertainty of any other impacts from the efforts than not having time to be in the field anymore - made many feel a sense of resignation and disconnection from the practical impact of their efforts.

Importantly, this sense of resignation did not stem from the act of reporting itself. All companies had experience working with one or more sustainability frameworks in the past. As CSO8 explained, "We've worked with Norwegian Transparency Act and Miljøfyrtårnet and gotten valuable information." The difference now lies in the complexity and heightened level of abstraction introduced by the CSRD. Instead of reporting being a practice that creates understanding and actionable possibilities for improvement, it was increasingly experienced as "answering for the sake of answering," as CSO8 put it. Reflecting on the potential outcomes, they added "if we get five truly valuable things to focus on as a company, then great. Would I bet on that happening? Not really. But hey - would be cool if it did."

As we've seen, much of the friction CSOs experienced stemmed from the new ways of valuing risks—shifting sustainability into the realm of speculative, financialized futures. By contrast, the concept of opportunities remained more familiar, still grounded in prospects for environmental improvement or financial gain. However, even here a growing tension emerged: as reporting demands expanded, many CSOs worried that the work of developing and implementing sustainability initiatives would increasingly be replaced. Although the IRO methodology introduces new ways of doing sustainability - especially through the lens of risk - the idea of opportunities largely retains its earlier form. Opportunities still refer to prospects for increased cash flow or improvements in climate and environmental performance. As CSO4 explained, although "as a developer, constructing buildings destroys natural areas permanently," there are also opportunities for "positive impact," for example through "redeveloping a parking lot into a building with green areas on the roof and in shared spaces, contributing to ecological restoration." While the opportunity perspective highlights the potential for positive change, it is increasingly overshadowed by the demands of extensive

reporting, which risk pulling resources away from actual sustainability work. As CSO8 succinctly stated, "I want to go out and do things".

This sense of tension - between doing and documenting - also helps explain a broader organizational shift described by many informants. As sustainability reporting becomes increasingly modified through risk metrics, forward-looking valuations, and financial performance indicators, responsibility for the report often migrates toward those already fluent in financial logic. While most of the CSOs interviewed have been producing sustainability reports in some way previously, the changes to reporting as introduced by the CSRD, has shifted, and a broader agreement emerged that "the natural owner of the report is the Chief Financial Officer" (CSO9), with some "placing responsibility (...) under the corporate accounting manager," (CSO9) with some companies assigning it to the corporate accounting manager, or staffing sustainability teams with professionals "coming from the accounting and audit side of things" (CSO5). This configuration makes sense within the CSRD's logic: the sustainability report is to be written in the language of financial reporting, cross-referenced with financial disclosures, and published as part of the same reporting package (EU 2023/2772, 2023, ESRS E1, App. A, AR. 77). Finance, therefore, becomes the final link in the chain of translation - where earlier efforts are shaped into a formal, auditable product. At the same time, this handoff to finance was not just procedural. For many informants, it also carried strategic weight: assigning formal ownership to the CFO was seen as a way to elevate the importance of sustainability - and to protect it from becoming "just a reporting practice" (CSO11). In some cases, it was also viewed as a way to free up time and space for more substantive sustainability work to take place beyond the reporting process itself.

Thus, while the company as a whole is cited to benefit from the CSRD, the everyday realities faced by CSOs are quite different. It is important to recognize that CSOs - whether directly or by proxy through the companies they represent - are only one group among the intended beneficiaries of the CSRD reporting process. From the perspective of most CSOs, the assumptions, projections, and scenario-based disclosures demanded by the CSRD often feel abstract or disconnected from the practical work of identifying concrete, actionable interventions, and as a result, the reporting process can seem overly focused on speculation rather than tangible impact. This sense of arbitrariness - the feeling that the lines they must adhere to are drawn in shifting sand - surfaced repeatedly in interviews. As CSO2 put it, much of the work "is not an exact science." Yet, the fact that the process may feel disconnected for CSOs, does not mean it lacks meaning for others. From the standpoint of investors, the same assumptions and forward-looking metrics may not only appear appropriate but even essential for assessing risk exposure and the long-term financial viability of potential investments. As a result, many experience this process as a bureaucratic mandate that demands speculation cloaked in the formal language of financial rationality. In translating their work and experiences into financialized valuation methods, many of the situated realities and knowledges of CSOs risk being flattened as they are reinterpreted through these valuation devices.

4.2.1.2 Drowned in Translations

As we have seen, as sustainability reporting under the CSRD unfolds, professional judgment emerges as both a necessity and a source of friction. Translating complex, context-specific practices into standardized audit-ready formats is not a straightforward task, but one that requires ongoing negotiation between CSOs, auditors, and consultants. This section traces how sustainability knowledge is modified, contested, and at times diminished through the chains of translation that link practical sustainability work to disclosure templates. The promise of the CSRD is clear: greater transparency, stronger sustainability governance, and standardized reporting. Yet for many CSOs, the process of implementation feels less like creating transparency - and producing legibility - that is, making their work visible and verifiable according to external standards that may obscure as much as they reveal. Rather than clarifying sustainability practices, implementation often feels like getting lost in translation.

As we saw in Part 1, auditors often serve as the first point of contact for CSOs during the implementation of the CSRD. But their role does not end there. Auditors also approve the final report, a process that typically involves repeated interactions and negotiations between the two actors. In doing so, they help shape what information circulates, how it is framed, and what is deemed credible. Positioned as obligatory passage points (Law, 1986) - sites through which information must pass and be transformed - auditors have become indispensable to the sustainability reporting network.

Although the "relative" (CSO2) nature of what auditors ask for serves as a point of tension in this process, making it hard to "understand what they're asking for." The exercise becomes less about providing clear disclosures and more about interpreting shifting expectations. A few CSOs "didn't initially realize that we needed sources to support our claims. We thought we could rely on our own assessments." (CSO2). This lack of clarity runs alongside another disconnection: as CSOs attempt to navigate ambiguous reporting requirements, they simultaneously experience a growing distance from the substantive sustainability work they once led. Several CSOs described the reporting process as increasingly bureaucratic - a "checklist exercise" (CSO8) - where sustainability efforts are being obscured by formatting and procedural demands (CSO9). The frustration with the complexity and time burden is captured in CSO5's reflection:

Let's just hope that this practice isn't designed just to maximize billable hours for auditors, but also makes the reported information accessible and understandable for those who actually need to use it.

Similar frustrations were voiced by others: "This is also a way for auditors to train their new employees - while getting the client to pay for it" (CSO1), and "we wondered, 'is this just busywork for an industry that needs something to do?'" (CSO6). For some CSOs, the relationship with auditors was seen as instrumental, even as it remained tense. As one explained, while they had to be cautious in navigating these relationships, they "are still completely dependent on them to reach our goals" because "the workload is too overwhelming for us to handle alone" (CSO6).

This tension points to a deeper concern: that the reporting process, rather than facilitating meaningful sustainability action, is becoming increasingly detached from "the operational realities of what we do, that to me is the most important" (CSO6). As they went on to emphasize, the priority should be "that we actually reduce energy consumption and pollution, not just that we report on it." This shift highlights a central dynamic identified by Power (1999): the shift from direct observation or intervention to second-order of control: a form of oversight focused less on tangible outcomes and more on the presence of systems and procedures. The abstraction experienced by CSOs is encapsulated by CSO8's blunt summary: "Basically, it's just a checklist exercise - 'Do they have an answer for this?' 'Do they have an answer for that'" (CSO8).

At the company level, all the CSOs I interviewed described the CSRD as overwhelming. This feeling was not solely due to the directive's length, complexity, or time necessarily allocated to it - although it was referred to as "overkill" (CSO8). Spanning thousands of pages filled with legal language, disclosure requirements, and extensive guidance, the directive often felt impenetrable. As CSO1 put in, "I tried reading those guides and documents from EFRAG, but I stood no chance," said CSO1. However, beyond the sheer volume of material, it was the prescribed lens of seeing - and the necessary translation of sustainability practices into the language of audit - that contributed most to the sense of disconnection. While none of the CSOs I interviewed were lawyers, many came from technical or applied backgrounds, engineering, HR, economics, and described the directive's highly formal, abstract language as difficult to engage with (CSO1; CSO2; CSO8). Having auditors positioned as both the first and final link in the chain of translation only deepened this effect. As CSO9 reflected on their participation in the auditors training program, "Their approach is very rigid - they have a strict, rules-based mindset, but lack an understanding of the industry."

Regardless of background, the sustainability issues these CSOs work with, such as waste systems, building materials, or energy use, must now be translated into abstract, forward-looking, financially-framed disclosures. For some (CSO2; CSO3; CSO5; CSO9), this sense of disconnection becomes even more pronounced in their interactions with auditors. CSO9 noted that there was "no interest in understanding the context of our work", a sentiment echoed by several other CSOs. Others described sustainability reporting as reduced to "a schematic checklist exercise" (CSO5) with a feeling that CSOs and auditors were constantly "talking past each other" (CSO2). As discussed earlier, many CSOs already felt distanced from the core of their work, with several expressing that they now "only have time to report" (CSO1), or that reporting has become what they do "all day, every day" (CSO2). Against this backdrop, translating rich, context-specific sustainability work into the technical and financial language of auditing not only reshaped how their efforts were communicated, but also how they were understood and valued. This translation process, in turn, privileged certain types of knowledge and certain professional roles, particularly those with financial or auditing expertise, while sidelining the situated, practical experience many CSOs bring to the table. As formulated by CSO11: "I find it a bit worrying that sustainability is being replaced by just numbers and check-boxes, and that the actual field - the expertise and the experiences built up over time - is no longer really being seen."

The frustration many CSOs felt about their own expertise and experience being sidelined was heightened by what they perceived as the illogical structure and focus of the ESRS. When CSOs began engaging with these standards, many described them as confusing or inconsistent (CSO2; CSO6; CSO8; CSO10). Some noted that the standards "don't seem to be developed by people with technical experience" (CSO10) or remarked, as CSO11 did, that they "seem very academically designed, by people who maybe haven't actually worked hands-on with sustainability themselves." Others pointed to the internal inconsistencies, describing the standards as "repetitive and overlapping constantly" (CSO5), or that they "seem to have been made by different academic bodies that maybe haven't really talked to each other" (CSO11). Many expressed frustration not just with the content, but with the translation demands imposed by the reporting process - especially when their existing experience in sustainability work felt devalued. CSO5, for instance, emphasized the difficulty of the formatting process, stating that although they have worked with sustainability reporting for 15 years and are arriving at similar substantive results, translating their work into the CSRD's reporting format is "super hard." CSO3 put it more bluntly: "The whole system feels more like something designed by auditors than by sustainability professionals." While EFRAG, as previously discussed, recruited sustainability, social, and financial experts to contribute to the ESRS, the translation practices it prescribes still create the experience of privileging certain types of knowledge - particularly financial and auditing expertise at the expense of situated, practical sustainability experience.

While some CSOs described feeling disconnected from the audit-driven perspectives they were expected to align with, others recounted more explicit confrontations with auditors, with negotiations that sometimes turned heated. For most, the relationship was not just about receiving guidance or support, but about defending their experience and expertise. As CSO2 put it, "I have no problem defending this to an auditor," highlighting that interactions could involve standing firm against competing interpretations. CSO9 shared a concrete example of a disagreement: "We ended up in a heated debate just three minutes into our first meeting with the advisors." The conflict centered on how to define risk. The advisor argued that even if a company complies with strict environmental laws, activities that involve pollution or land use inherently carry the potential for harm - and should therefore be treated as risks. From the CSO's perspective, however, would overwhelm the system and make it impossible to prioritize what truly matters:

That was the core debate—how do we balance acknowledging environmental risks while also recognizing that we operate as a commercial real estate company? Yes, real estate development is not inherently environmentally friendly, but it provides housing, which is essential for building better cities and improving living conditions.

This points to one of the deeper reasons behind the disconnection many CSOs describe. It is not only that their expertise feels undervalued, or that the reporting standards fail to reflect sector-specific realities. It is that their work is increasingly modified through the narrow lens of what counts as *decision-relevant* information to the *users* of sustainability reports. Their efforts

are translated into terms of risks and opportunities - past, present, or future - tied to potential capital gains or losses. For many, this framing is far removed from what they see as the core of their role: designing and building infrastructures that serve communities while minimizing environmental harm. The shift in focus - from producing something people in cities or towns can live in, visit, use to generating abstract reports for abstract users - creates a fundamental disconnect between the work CSOs are trying to do and what they are now being asked to report.

4.2.1.3 Negotiating Sustainability

Faced with overwhelming expectations, CSOs adopted different approaches to how broadly they would begin the reporting process, in other words, CSOs did not react passively to the complexity and uncertainty imposed by the CSRD. Instead, some engaged strategically, adopting different approaches to how broadly they would begin the reporting process. Some CSOs aimed to follow the CSRD's instructions more comprehensively, starting wide and attempting to map as much of their company as possible to gain full overview. However, more frequently, CSOs took a cautious approach, wary of taking on too much at once. As CSO1 put it, the goal was to avoid "floundering more than necessarily." They described their initial strategy:

Our initial step was to create a color-coding system, where we identified:

- Optional disclosures that we chose to exclude.
- Disclosures that can be phased in over one to three years, which we also set aside.
- The remaining disclosures, which we assessed to determine if they are mandatory for 2024.

Choosing not to report on anything beyond what was mandatory was certainly one tactic for simplifying the process, but efforts at simplification went even further. As CSO1 explained, their consultant had "consulted with their auditors and a consultancy," who pointed out that the narrative data points (textual data-points) which "amounts to 70% (...) can't actually be verified by the auditors." Based on this advice, CSO1 concluded that it might not be necessary to elaborate on every area immediately: "We believe we might be able to simplify things a bit". Others agreed with the approach of starting narrow, as stated by CSO3: "We are not trying to avoid responsibility - we want to do things correctly and focus on what is truly relevant," but that an extensive process in the beginning would be "overwhelming and impractical." Concluding that "Since we are adapting to a new system, we decided to start small and gradually expand."

Although these tactics were not uncommon, not all CSOs agreed with this approach. CSO2, in particular, viewed it as a form of avoidance. They argued that the reasoning some companies used to exclude certain topics was "an argument that is harder to make," especially when the company's activities clearly had an impact. As CSO2 put it:

They believe that, 'We, as a small real estate company, don't have any impact on this.' But then it also becomes difficult to stand by that when you know that we *do* have an impact.

The frustration voiced by CSO2 can be read not only as a concern about companies evading responsibility, but also as a complication of one of the CSRD's promises to CSOs: that the commensuration of sustainability data - and the rankings that follow - would strategically benefit genuinely sustainable companies. In practice, however, the flexibility embedded in the CSRD, and maneuvering space it created, means that the results produced remain difficult to compare and may undermine the very transparency the directive seeks to achieve.

This dynamic of flexibility can be better understood through Power's work on audit cultures. Power 1999 argues that audits derive much of their influence from their vagueness. Designed to address uncertainty and risk, audits promote broad ideals of transparency and accountability - ideals whose meanings shift depending on the context. This ambiguity makes auditing techniques highly adaptable across industries and domains, while still projecting an image of legitimacy. The very flexibility that makes audits powerful, Power suggests, also conceals how much negotiation underpin them. This lens helps explain why the CSRD's reliance on audit mechanisms does not prevent strategic interpretation or negotiations - in fact, it enables it, hiding the process behind an image of rationality. A common dynamic in this process for all CSOs is negotiations as a central part of the reporting process - therefore reporting is not just about securing the correct data, but about shaping how sustainability issues are framed and understood.

This process of negotiation represents the final form of disconnection examined in this section. It occurs at the sharp end of the translation chain, where sustainability work is ultimately transformed into reportable outputs. Perhaps recognizing the central role that negotiations play in shaping these outcomes, CSO10 captured the resulting sense of distortion succinctly: "it doesn't really describe reality." Another echo of this is captured by CSO8:

Biggest challenges? Capacity, time and the risk of answering "wrong." And "wrong" doesn't even mean incorrect— just that some answers carry more weight than others. But who decides which questions are more important? It's not us. So suddenly, it feels like someone is overriding our responses. And then you find yourself adjusting answers after the fact to get the final scores to "look right." At that point, it kind of feels like... cheating.

This experience echoes Power's 1999 broader critique: audits work because they *appear* scientific and objective to those outside of the process, even though the processes behind them remain discretionary and opaque. In the case of sustainability reporting under the CSRD, the audit process does not eliminate uncertainty; rather, it reshapes the reporting environment to fit predefined structures and performance measures. Sustainability data must be made "auditable" - not by resolving ambiguity, but by organizing complexity into standardized, verifiable forms. In doing so, the CSRD extends the logic of audit cultures: presenting sustainability disclosures as stable facts, even as many CSOs experience them as disconnected

from the situated realities they are meant to represent.

4.2.1.4 Making Sense Together: The Use and Creation of Sector-Specific Networks

Faced with audit-driven reporting structures that often feel disconnected from operational realities, CSOs are not passive recipients of these demands. Instead, they actively construct alternative systems for sense-making and support. In absence of clear understanding, many CSOs turn to peers in other companies to co-construct meaning. Informal networks such as lunch meetings (CSO3; CSO6), phone calls (CSO5; CSO10), and recurring sector initiatives (CSO2; CSO4; CSO7; CSO9; CSO11) - have become crucial tools for reinterpreting the CSRD's demands. These forums function as spaces for collective sense-making, where CSOs compare outputs, create provisional standards, and calibrate their internal strategies. The drive to establish industry-specific "best practices" appears to stem not only from the complexity of the reporting requirements but also from a broader sense that generic frameworks do not always capture the specificities of different sectors. Although sector-specific standards are currently being developed by EFRAG, these apply to areas such as agriculture, financial institutions, and textiles - not construction, housing, or city development (EFRAG, n.d.). This dynamic aligns with prior research showing that actors do not simply conform to prescribed metrics or rules - they interpret, negotiate, and occasionally subvert them to make regulations workable within their own contexts (Cusworth et al., 2023; Demortain, 2024; Pelizza & Van Rossem, 2024; Pollock et al., 2018).

Across the real estate sector, a range of collaborative initiatives have emerged to help companies navigate the complexity of CSRD reporting. Some are formal, such as joint projects organized between the Grønn Byggallianse (Green Building Alliance) and Norsk Eiendom (Norwegian Real Estate), while others are more informal - networks of sustainability officers from "rival firms" (CSO9). Many of these initiatives serve as platforms for peer support and collective sense-making. As CSO3 put it: "Something this industry is quite good at is being open and trying to communicate the connections [between what is required and how to do it] and make each other better." CSO7 described how a small initial group of four companies grew into a network of eight, where meetings "initially planned for two hours - often extend to four hours due to the sheer amount of discussion." These meetings provided not only practical insights but also a shared learning environment. "Most of us are learning as we go," CSO7 continued, "alongside everyone else working in this space, because there's been so much training and (...) new directives, new regulations that no one could have predicted until they were already in this role." They concluded: It's really a case of learning by doing, together with others who are navigating the same challenges." This statement highlights how CSOs are not merely adapting to external demands, but actively participating in the co-creation of a new knowledge practice - one that is being shaped in real time through shared experimentation, and collaboration.

Rather than producing uniform assessments, these discussions support informed decision-making in a space still marked by ambiguity. As CSO6 noted: "While we don't necessarily copy each other's assessments, these discussions help us make informed decisions in what is still a new and complex process." The value of these arenas becomes even clearer when considering

the ongoing uncertainty around what CSRD compliance actually entails. CSO1 shared: "I personally spent part of my summer analyzing company websites and annual reports" to try to understand how others approached double materiality. Similarly, CSO5, reflected on reviewing reports previously praised for their quality, only to conclude that, by this year's standards, "they did not seem very well done." For many, meeting CSRD expectations feels like trying to hit a constantly shifting target.

Several CSOs emphasized that their approach to the CSRD is strategic. This is not out of desire "to evade responsibility" (CSO3), but because a gradual approach is seen as the most effective way to build understanding. In a landscape marked by uncertainty, the goal becomes delivering enough to meet expectations without "drowning" (CSO1). As CSO3 explained, the point is "not to cut corners, but to understand which topics truly apply to us." Their strategy involves working thoroughly with a few topics first to gain familiarity with the methodology, before expanding toward a more holistic assessment. However, this incremental approach is not without critique. CSO2 pointed out that many companies have taken a conservative stance in setting materiality thresholds, often narrowing their reporting scope for practical reasons or because they assume limited impact, stating that "although our individual impact may seem minor on a global scale, as an industry we have a significant impact in Norway." A deeper issue underlying this is the uncertainty around scale - specifically what reference point companies should use when evaluating their significance. Should materiality be judged against global environmental effect, national relevance, or industry-specific practices?

This uncertainty is not uncommon. One example comes from CSO6, who, when unsure whether a topic should be considered material, cross-checked reporting templates and compared their company's activities with other sectors. For instance, while "we build near the sea," they questioned whether this risk constituted a material risk when compared to sectors like fishing or aquaculture. "Does building a house by the sea count as polluting when compared to discarded fishing nets?" The comparison raised a deeper dilemma: if both are classified as material, does that suggest they are equally harmful? And conversely, does the presence of more obvious or severe harms risk rendering smaller, context-specific impacts invisible? These exercises offered no clear answers, but they reflected a broader need for clarity of scope and relevance. A need that, in turn, fuels the formation of collaborative spaces where companies can co-develop interpretations of materiality.

This sense of uncertainty was echoed by CSO2 "(...) it might actually be intended for another industry. So, going deeper into the material means understanding which ESRS requirements truly apply to us." Several CSOs emphasized that sector-specific collaboration provides not only practical support, but also recognition of the local context of construction. As CSO10 notes, "It does seem like some of the people working on these standards don't have a clear understanding of how things function on construction sites." One reason sector-specific initiatives have become so important is that they offer a sense of community and shared - relevance - a space where CSOs can affirm the value of their industry-specific knowledge and push back against general frameworks not adapted to fit their reality. In this way, sectoral collaboration becomes a counterweight to the perceived disconnect between standard-

setters and practitioners. As CSO5 critically observed: "the audit regime (revisorstanden) - particularly the five or six largest firms - is developing a new framework that is difficult to grasp, and in some cases, may be disconnected from the realities of certain companies" (CSO5).

Regardless of the strategies CSOs believed were right for their own companies, or the approaches recommended by their auditors, many found value in comparing both interpretations *and* outcomes with others. These informal exchanges - whether over lunch (CSO3), during long multi-hour meetings (CSO7), or simply through "chatting with people in the same position as me" (CSO5) - offered space to reflect on just how varied reporting practices and results could be. The variation adds another layer of disconnect - one that undermines the perceived legitimacy and reliability of the process. Several informants noted that even within the same sector - Norwegian real estate - companies operating under similar sustainability conditions still ended up with strikingly different assessments. As CSO9 put it: "Surprisingly, we got completely different results - even though we operate in the exact same market. That's a problem." CSO2 similarly reflected that this "clearly highlights how subjectivity plays a major role in these assessments, making the outcomes less consistent than they ideally should be." The inconsistency contributes to a broader sense that the CSRD reporting process does not always produce accurate or meaningful reflections of a company's sustainability performance. Instead, it can feel arbitrary - shaped more by interpretation, translation, and the perspectives of individual CSOs, consultants, or auditors than by the underlying realities of the company's operations. As stated by CSO9 "If we're supposed to benchmark companies, but everyone evaluates risks differently, then benchmarking doesn't work. So, we're now pushing for industry-wide standards, because sector-wide comparability is critical."

This leads brings us to another key aim of sector-wide networks: the development of shared standards. Some of the larger and more formal initiatives seek to create sector-wide double materiality assessments and long-lists of material topics, in an effort to standardize the materiality process. This reflects Pollock's 2018 observation that organizations rarely conform to passively external demands; instead they often enact reflexivity, actively interpreting and reshaping those demands in ways that align with their own context and capacities. A similar dynamic is described by Demortain 2024 in his study of how predictive models became embedded in regulatory practice within the chemical industry. These models were not simply technical tools, but sites of negotiation between companies and regulators, shaping how knowledge - particularly around chemical safety - was defined and validated. Importantly, expertise did not remain fixed within regulatory bodies. Instead, it moved between actors through collaborative modeling practices, blurring the line between compliance and co-production. While my case differs - focusing on reporting standards rather than predictive models - the underlying practice of distributed expertise is strikingly similar. Rather than a single actor like EFRAG dictating how reporting should be done, sector-based initiatives in real estate allow professionals to contribute their own situated expertise, actively influencing how standards are developed and applied in practice. These networks of professionals negotiate, test, and shape reporting practices, building what can be seen as a distinct knowledge practice - much like Demortain's modelers shaped the construction of predictive regimes. In both cases, we see that tools are never just neutral instruments - they become embedded in broader

negotiations and practices, and their meaning is shaped through interactions. Expertise, rather than being imposed from the top down, circulates through professional networks.

But this shift toward sector-wide standards is not welcomed by all. Both CSO2 and CSO5 expressed concerns about the direction and implications of this development. For CSO5, the primary issue was one of complexity and fit. As they noted, "companies don't fit neatly into a standard," and the level of granularity required could demand "a huge system to support them." The fear is that uniform standards may impose rigid structures on organizations whose operations don't align cleanly with the assumed sectoral archetype. CSO2, by contrast, raised concerns about the lack of predictability. "The challenge is you don't really know what is coming," they explained, highlighting the mixed messages around the sector-specific standards. "Some say that the sector-wide standards will make it even more extensive. But at the same time, they say it will be made less extensive. So it's hard to know how much change there will be going forward."

In sum, this section has shown that once sustainability inputs are gathered, the challenge does not end - it deepens. As companies begin to assess these inputs through the lens of Impacts, Risks, and Opportunities, they enter a new phase of translation: one that requires forecasting uncertain futures, aligning internal perspectives with regulatory expectations, and navigating negotiations with auditors. These processes expose new frictions: between professional expertise and prescriptive frameworks, between action and abstraction, and between sustainability as lived practice and sustainability as auditable disclosure. Rather than resolving ambiguity, the IRO process often intensifies it - prompting CSOs to seek collective clarity through peer networks and informal collaborations. These efforts are not just technical - they are interpretive, strategic, and deeply situated. Yet even this provisional meaning-making must eventually be formalized. The next step in the reporting process requires that all of this interpretive labor - situated insights, negotiated risks, and imagined futures - be transformed once again: into standardized, spreadsheet-based disclosures that meet the formatting requirements of the ESRS. It is to this final stage of translation that we now turn.

4.2.2 From Judgment to Grid-lines

If assessing impacts, risks, and opportunities marked a shift toward interpretation and projection, the next phase of the CSRD process brings with it a different kind of challenge: flattening. The tensions CSOs experience in translating situated sustainability knowledge into standardized spreadsheets become even more acute when future uncertainties must be inscribed into pre-defined reporting categories. While the previous section examined how sustainability data under the CSRD is shaped by anticipatory tools, underlying assumptions, and negotiations, this section turns to the next critical step: formatting those data into the standardized spreadsheet set by EFRAG. The CSRD does not merely require that companies collect and analyze sustainability information - it demands that they translate these varied, often qualitative assessments into pre-defined reporting structures. This transformation process introduces a new layer of interpretation and constraint, as rich, context-specific knowledge must be condensed, labeled, and reorganized to fit pre-established categories. In

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	
2	ESRS	DR	Paragraf	Related A	Name	Data Type	Conditional alternative Cr	May (V)	Appendix B - ESRS 2 (SFDR + PILLAR 3 + Benchmark + CL)	Appendix C - ESRS 1 (DPIs subject to phased-in)	
3	ESRS 2	MDR-P	65 a	AR 21	Description of key contents of policy	narrative					
4	ESRS 2	MDR-P	65 b		Description of scope of policy or of its exclusions	narrative					
5	ESRS 2	MDR-P	65 c		Description of most senior level in organisation that is accountable for implementation of policy	narrative					
6	ESRS 2	MDR-P	65 d		Disclosure of third-party standards or initiatives that are respected through implementation of policy	narrative	Conditional				
7	ESRS 2	MDR-P	65 e		Description of consideration given to interests of key stakeholders in setting policy	narrative	Conditional				
8	ESRS 2	MDR-P	65 f		Explanation of whether and how policy is made available to potentially affected stakeholders and stakeholders who need to help implement	narrative	Conditional				
9	ESRS 2	MDR-A	68 a	AR 22	Disclosure of key action	narrative	Conditional				
10	ESRS 2	MDR-A	68 b		Description of scope of key action	narrative	Conditional				
11	ESRS 2	MDR-A	68 c		Time horizon under which key action is to be completed	semi-narrative	Conditional				
12	ESRS 2	MDR-A	68 d		Description of key action taken, and its results, to provide for and cooperate in or support provision of remedy for those harmed by action	narrative	Conditional				
13	ESRS 2	MDR-A	68 e		Disclosure of quantitative and qualitative information regarding progress of actions or action plans disclosed in prior periods	narrative	Conditional				
14	ESRS 2	MDR-A	69 a		Disclosure of the type of current and future financial and other resources allocated to the action plan (Capex and Opex)	narrative	Conditional				
15	ESRS 2	MDR-A	69 b		Explanation of how current financial resources relate to most relevant amounts presented in financial statements	narrative	Conditional				
16	ESRS 2	MDR-A	AR 23		Current and future financial resources allocated to action plan, reassessed by time horizon and resources	Table/monetary	Conditional	V			
17	ESRS 2	MDR-A	69 b		Current financial resources allocated to action plan (Capex)	Monetary	Conditional				
18	ESRS 2	MDR-A	69 b		Current financial resources allocated to action plan (Opex)	Monetary	Conditional				
19	ESRS 2	MDR-A	69 c		Future financial resources allocated to action plan (Capex)	Monetary	Conditional				
20	ESRS 2	MDR-A	69 c		Future financial resources allocated to action plan (Opex)	Monetary	Conditional				
21	ESRS 2	MDR-M	75		Description of metrics used to evaluate performance and effectiveness, in relation to material impact, risk or opportunity	narrative					
22	ESRS 2	MDR-M	77 a		Disclosure of methodologies and significant assumptions behind metrics	narrative					
23	ESRS 2	MDR-M	77 b		Type of external body other than assurance provider that provides validation	narrative					
24	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 a	AR 24 - AR 26	Relationship with policy objectives	narrative					
25	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 b	AR 24 - AR 26	Measurable target	Decimal/Percent/narrative					
26	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 b	AR 24 - AR 26	Nature of target	semi-narrative	Conditional				
27	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 c	AR 24 - AR 26	Description of scope of target	narrative					
28	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 d	AR 24 - AR 26	Baseline value	Integer					
29	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 d	AR 24 - AR 26	Baseline year	Integer					
30	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 e	AR 24 - AR 26	Period to which target applies	semi-narrative					
31	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 e	AR 24 - AR 26	Indication of milestones or interim targets	narrative	Conditional				
32	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 f	AR 24 - AR 26	Description of methodologies and significant assumptions used to define target	narrative					
33	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 g	AR 24 - AR 26	Target related to environmental matters is based on conclusive scientific evidence	semi-narrative					
34	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 h	AR 24 - AR 26	Disclosure of whether and how stakeholders have been involved in target setting	narrative					
35	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 i	AR 24 - AR 26	Description of any changes in target and corresponding metrics or underlying measurement methodologies, significant assumptions, limitations	narrative					
36	ESRS 2	MDR-T	80 j	AR 24 - AR 26	Description of performance against disclosed target	narrative					
37	Disclosures to be reported in case the undertaking has not adopted policies and/or actions or set any measurable outcome-oriented targets (see chapter 4.3 MDR, ESRS 2)										
38											
39	ESRS 2	MDR-P	62		Disclosure of reasons for not having adopted policies	narrative	Conditional				
40	ESRS 2	MDR-P	62		Disclosure of timeframe in which the undertaking aims to adopt policies	narrative	Conditional	V			
41	ESRS 2	MDR-A	62		Disclosure of reasons for not having adopted actions	narrative	Conditional				

Figure 4.4: This figure presents a snapshot of the standardized reporting template issued by EFRAG under the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS). The template is organized into discrete fields and tables, each corresponding to specific disclosure requirements across environmental, social, and governance dimensions. This worksheet is taken from the Minimum Disclosure Requirement which must be filled regardless of materiality assessments

this step, sustainability becomes legible not only through what is evaluated, but through how it is rendered visible - boxed, sorted, and standardized.

While assumptions and professional judgment play a central role in the early stages of reporting, these judgments must ultimately be translated into standardized formats. One of the key tools prescribed to facilitate this translation is EFRAG's reporting template - a detailed Excel spreadsheet designed to structure materiality assessments, IROs and disclosures in line with CSRD's requirements. Yet this effort to formalize and streamline interpretation introduces a new layer of complexity. For many CSOs, the Excel sheet is not a helpful guide, but a demanding and often redundant tool that imposes rigid categorical structures onto what began as context-specific, interpretive work. What starts as a space for judgment and negotiations is gradually compressed into predefined drop-down menus and fixed disclosure boxes. This section examines how the EFRAG template shapes the reporting process - not only by trying to offer a *veneer of clarity*, but also by generating new frustrations, ambiguities, and constraints.

The Excel-based tool provided by EFRAG structures sustainability disclosures across 13 interconnected worksheets, each corresponding to general reporting requirements, or the materiality topics. These are aligned closely with the architecture of ESRS and are embedded with hyperlinks that lead users to dense legal documents. Navigating these documents is often a time-consuming and cognitively demanding task. For CSOs, the Excel sheet is not merely a data entry tool, but an interface between structured technical bureaucracy and situated organizational judgment - requiring constant movement between rigid templates and ambiguous legal formulations.

The experience of encountering the EFRAG spreadsheet is well captured by CSO9, who

described it as both overwhelming and obscuring meaning. For them, the rigid structure of the tool, combined with the heavy reliance on supplementary legal documents, made it difficult not only to navigate the process but to understand the underlying intent behind the disclosures, introducing another layer of opacity in the process. As CSO9 put it:

Yes, yes, it is actually quite... how should I put it? Difficult to describe, but a very complex task. Because it works within a very heavy regulatory framework, which includes a number of guiding documents and examples that must be considered (...). The tool itself is very rigid. It is structured with text boxes, and there are difficult questions that make it hard to see the bigger picture. This is one of our main challenges because CSRD is inherently difficult to understand and grasp, and it is hard to see the intent behind it. We had hoped that these tools would visualize the value of the reporting, but instead, they feel more like a bureaucratic treadmill. Unfortunately.

Zooming back out to the CSRD's broader problem formulation, the directive builds on the idea that better reporting will lead to better identification - and ultimately better management - of risks and opportunities (Directive 2022/2464/EU, rec. 12). It represents an investment in accountability through tools of transparency. As previously discussed, this process as studied by Freidberg (2020) and Ghosh (2023), have shown that the demand for accountability through metrics, indicators, and quantifiable disclosures create paradoxical effects. The process of rendering complex realities through calculative devices - as seen earlier in the case of IROs - is not a straightforward path towards greater visibility. Instead, the very act of reporting, as we will see through the use of this spreadsheet, can itself obstruct visibility.

This section traces how the structure and volume of reporting affects visibility on two fronts: first, for those tasked with producing the reports; and second, for those meant to "use" them. For CSOs, the intensive formatting and volume of required disclosures fragments their understanding of sustainability processes, making it difficult to maintain a coherent overview of how issues interrelate. In this way, the reporting structure not only disconnects CSOs from their own work but also undermines the CSRD's ambition to serve as a tool for better internal decision-making or external transparency. The final sustainability reports risk becoming too inaccessible to read and too fragmented to act upon - creating a view of sustainability that is simultaneously exhaustive and incoherent.

Two key problems emerge when encountering this spreadsheet: the loss of meaningful coherence, and the persistence of ambiguity despite standardization efforts. The spreadsheet itself offers a striking visualization of the disconnect many CSOs describe. As discussed earlier, the shift from hands-on sustainability work to abstract reporting obligations has already distanced many from the substance of their practice. The design of the EFRAG spreadsheet exacerbated this distance by fragmenting the reporting process into isolated and disjointed prompts. This format echoes a broader experience among CSOs, who report feeling increasingly detached from the substance of sustainability work as it becomes fragmented into procedural exercises. As CSO5 noted, "the way it's structured now with EFRAG and those massive spreadsheets with 1,276 data points - it's just an incredibly heavy and complex thing

to navigate.” Rather than supporting reflection or meaning-making, the format often compels isolated justifications for each cell, undermining any coherent narrative of sustainability performance. As CSO9 noted, the results is a reporting process where it becomes “harder to extract meaning,” let alone maintain a sense of purpose in the information being produced.

To illustrate the volume and disjointed nature of the worksheets, CSO1 noted, "So this one starts on line 3 and continues down to line 200." CSO8, who had previously expressed skepticism toward the method to conduct a "full 360-degree evaluation," was even more direct when asked whether the process was useful:

No. Not when you're answering a thousand questions. They could have condensed it to 50, and that would have been insightful. But when you're buried in sheer volume, the whole thing loses meaning. It's overkill.

They elaborated further on how the overwhelming structure of the tool undercut its original purpose:

What was expected was pretty straightforward. You could ask questions, and in many cases, there weren't hard numbers or facts - a lot of it was subjective judgment. We had to agree on "What do we stand for?" and "What do we realistically achieve?" But the system itself - the whole process of answering it all - was *extremely* complex. A lot of things overlapped, so even though the questions were easy to answer, we spent so much time discussing them that by the end, I wasn't even sure what I was actually answering. I'll be honest about that.

This loss of perspective is compounded by persistent ambiguity. Despite the rigid structure of the template, many CSOs described the process of completing it as confusing and uncertain. Unclear definitions and vague prompts left much of the reporting work open to interpretation. As CSO9 put it, "understanding each ESRS takes 3–4 hours of cross-disciplinary discussions. It's a heavy process." Even seemingly simple concepts, such as how to report on gender balance in leadership, became sites of confusion: "how do we distinguish between an executive team, a board, and senior management?" (CSO7). Instead of offering clarity, the documentation required CSOs to engage in what CSO2 described as a process of "one step forward, two steps back" - another cycle of deciphering rather than delivering actionable transparency.

Beyond the rigidity of the reporting templates lies another persistent challenge: enduring ambiguity despite formal standardization. Although the CSRD is accompanied by extensive guidance documents and examples, many CSOs describe a lingering sense of uncertainty about whether—and how—specific standards apply to their organizations. As CSO2 explained, “S3 and S4 are somewhat challenging for us because we work extensively with local communities through urban development projects,” yet the standards seem tailored toward more direct industrial harms like displacement. Before diving into what this causes, I want to turn to the site CSO2 should, according to the CSRD, turn to to answer this question; the ESRS Disclosure Guides (EU 2023/2772, 2023). In turning to the section explaining the Disclosure Requirement on material impacts on affected communities (ESRS S3), the examples offered - such as industrial plants and downstream pollution - are seemingly distant from CSO2's

daily work with local communities and urban development. Rather than providing clarity, the standards raise new questions: are these rules meant for us?

Disclosure Requirement related to ESRS 2 SBM-3 – Material impacts, risks and opportunities and their interaction with strategy and business model

8. When responding to ESRS 2 SBM-3 paragraph 48, the undertaking shall disclose:
 - (a) whether and how actual and potential impacts on **affected communities** as identified in ESRS 2 IRO-1 *Description of the processes to identify and assess material impacts, risks and opportunities* : (i) originate from or are connected to the undertaking's strategy and business models, and (ii) inform and contribute to adapting the undertaking's strategy and business model; and
 - (b) the relationship between its material risks and opportunities arising from impacts and **dependencies** on affected communities and its strategy and business model.
9. When fulfilling the requirements of paragraph 48, the undertaking shall disclose whether all **affected communities** who are likely to be materially impacted by the undertaking, including impacts that are connected with the undertaking's own operations and **value chain** , including through its products or services, as well as through its **business relationships** , are included in the scope of its disclosure under ESRS 2. In addition, the undertaking shall provide the following information:
 - (a) a brief description of the types of communities subject to material impacts by its own operations or through its upstream and downstream value chain, and specify whether they are:
 - i. communities living or working around the undertaking's operating **sites** , factories, facilities or other physical operations, or more remote communities affected by activities at those sites (for example by downstream water **pollution**);
 - ii. communities along the undertaking's value chain (for example, those affected by the operations of **suppliers** ' facilities or by the activities of logistics or distribution providers);
 - iii. communities at one or both endpoints of the value chain (for example, at the point of extraction of metals or minerals or harvesting of commodities, or communities around **waste** or **recycling** sites);
 - iv. communities of **indigenous peoples** .

Figure 4.5: The complexity and layering of qualifiers make it a challenging standard to interpret in practice.

This creates a dilemma: "We need to consider the underlying intent behind the standards and whether they truly apply to our context. At this point, we haven't fully decided whether we should include them or not." Similarly, CSO6 described the difficulty of interpreting the standard for marine ecosystems, questioning whether it applied merely because their company builds near coastlines: "Trying to understand [this] required extensive analysis to see if [it was] applicable to the company, and we still don't know." Such uncertainties not only delay reporting but shift the burden of interpretation onto sustainability teams, who must navigate vague definitions, cross-reference multiple legal documents, and infer legislative intent - often without clear resolution. In this sense, the template itself embodies a contradiction: it surrounds the reporting process with dense, technical implementation guides, yet leaves fundamental questions unanswered. As CSO7 reflected, "I tried reading those manuals, but I also found them very difficult to navigate."

The experience of navigating the artificial divides between overlapping standards is captured particularly vividly by CSO11:

So with climate, everything overlaps a bit, right? Some people have been responsible for greenhouse gases and worked on that, others have been responsible for energy, others for biodiversity, and so on. It feels like everyone has tried to be the best in their field and include absolutely everything, but without much real dialogue between the different disciplines. And importantly, without really considering the overall scope of what it would turn into. Instead of someone stepping back and asking, 'What's really the most important right now?', and tightening it later, it feels like they just fired a shotgun and tried to hit everything -

hitting the same things multiple times rather than cutting things down.

Together, these experiences reveal how the EFRAG template - despite its aim to structure and standardize sustainability reporting - often exacerbates the very problems it seeks to address. For the CSOs in this study, the spreadsheet often fragmented sustainability work into isolated disclosures, disconnected them from the strategic substance of their efforts, and burdened them with navigating persistent ambiguities hidden behind a facade of formal rigor. In trying to render sustainability information auditable and comparable, the template risks producing a landscape of disjointed, repetitive, and opaque reporting, where meaning is harder to extract, coherence is lost, and the promise of transparency becomes increasingly difficult to realize.

While the EFRAG template is intended to standardize and clarify sustainability disclosures, many CSOs describe it as producing the opposite effect: overwhelming repetition, overlapping content, and a flood of fragmented text fields. CSO9 aptly describes the process of filling information into the spreadsheet as a "bureaucratic treadmill" - raising a crucial question: who, if anyone, will this information truly serve? As CSOs struggled to fill in countless, often redundant cells, CSOs voiced a deeper fear: that without a willingness from "the audit profession (revisorstanden) and those defining these frameworks" to "meet us somewhere in the middle," the process would produce "a report that no one actually benefits from. And that is the real fear" (CSO5).

This phenomenon resembles what Lassiter et al. (2016) found in the context of biobanking, where standardization practices - originally intended to ensure ethical conduct and quality control - ultimately became performative rituals of accountability. Rather than strengthening substantive ethical reflection, the focus shifted toward procedural compliance, producing documentation that signaled responsibility without necessarily enhancing it. Similarly, from the perspective of several CSOs, the overwhelming structure of the EFRAG spreadsheet risks displacing the substantive goals of sustainability work. Rather than supporting meaningful evaluation or action, it was often experienced as encouraging a "bureaucratic treadmill" (CSO9).

Some CSOs described the spreadsheet as a kind of rigid recipe - one that, if you followed exactly, produces an unreadable result. "If you follow the EFRAG spreadsheet to the letter," said CSO5, "you end up with a document full of redundancies - incredibly unreadable". They explained that the artificial divisions between various standards force interconnected policies to be artificially separated from each other. "There are so many cross-references, making it clunky," that there is a lot of "'See section X' or 'Refer to page Y'. (...) Just the icing on the cake, right?". That not only gathering or assessing information is hard but that "gathering all this to fit together in a coherent and logical way takes a lot of effort - it's a job in itself" (CSO5). The contradictory nature of the EFRAG spreadsheet becomes even clearer when considering the tension between its heavy structure and the type of information it seeks to collect. While the reporting tool demands the completion of up to thousands of rigid, disjointed text boxes, "around 70% of CSRD requirements are narrative-based" (CSO1).

The issue is further stated by CSO9 who states that the goal is to consolidate the report from being "a 300-page document" to "ideally 40-50 pages". As well as instead of "maintaining 14-15

separate policies" to "instead streamline them into 2-3 core policies". Maybe that is a key insight here, that not only are the realities of sustainability situations lost in the reporting process, but the act of reporting and what it should amount to was lost in the standard development process. And other CSOs state that the process could be "refined a bit more - and still deliver the same value" (CSO11). And that "you have to remember that someone is supposed to read this on the other end" and a consequence of this, "if it becomes too much, too overwhelming, it becomes difficult to actually understand how the company is doing in terms of ESG" (CSO11).

For some, the experience of filling out the template not only complicates reporting but displaces the purpose of sustainability work altogether. As CSO11 reflected:

Yeah, no, so you kind of have to understand the context a bit, and start by picking the low-hanging fruit - before you start climbing all the way to the top to shake down the last pear up there. (...) We need people who can actually work on solutions - not just be really good at ticking boxes. Now I sound super negative, but I'm not. It's just the scale of this whole thing makes it feel like everything gets lost. You lose the good message and the original intention behind it (CSO11).

Together, these findings show how the CSRD's demands for calculability and auditability transform sustainability work into a chain of translations, where uncertainties are formalized and operational realities often fade into the background.

4.2.3 Reassembling Sustainability: A Practice Made Through Reporting

One of the key points of this analysis is that sustainability, especially through the CSRD, is not something that exists on its own. It emerges through the practice of reporting. It is made visible - and made real - through the ways it is represented. Following Latour (1990), it is the displacement of information and its movement across actors, tools, and formats that give inscriptions their meaning. The work of gathering, observing, translating, and selecting is essential. But if this work did not result in a report - if it had not been inscribed - would it have held any power? Would it have circulated, persuaded, or shaped decisions? Most likely not. This is why reporting is not just seen as describing sustainability; it is the process that creates sustainability as something that can be seen, shared, and acted upon. The final report gains power not through its ability to perfectly reflect reality, but because it pulls together complex activities, opinions, and priorities into a form that can move across companies, regulators, and investors. But this process also filters out a lot. Decisions about what to include, what to leave out, and how to frame the information shape what the report actually shows. What looks like an objective description is, in fact, the result of many choices and compromises along the way.

To illustrate this point, I turn to an example offered by Latour. He describes how Louis XVI tasked the explorer La Pérouse with traveling to what may have been a Chinese island or peninsula in order to draw a map. At first glance, this may seem like a simple mission of exploration. But its significance lies in the broader context: the production of an inscription - a map - was not just a technical act, but a political one. As Latour (1990, p. 25) notes, the ability to bring back such an inscription played a role in determining who could claim ownership

over a territory. This act of mapping cannot be separated from the "innovations in inscription" that made it possible: the instruments, tools, and practices - such as the compass or the paper - that enabled both the journey and the production of the map. Yet the map alone would be meaningless if it did not, as Latour writes, "bear on certain controversies and force dissenters into behaving in new ways." In other words, inscriptions matter because they shape future actions. They mobilize actors, gather knowledge, and stabilize new ways of seeing and acting in the world.

We can trace similar dynamics when studying the CSRD. Just as La Pérouse was tasked with producing a map, companies are tasked with producing a sustainability report. Although the processes of inscription today - the gathering of information, the translation into graphs or spreadsheets, and the final inclusion into a formal report - may seem more complex, the underlying dynamics are much the same. Actors are mobilized and assigned roles in this process: EFRAG designs criteria for how inscriptions should be made - how sustainability measures are to be translated into risks, opportunities and decision-relevant information, how data should be organized in spreadsheets, and how graphs should structure the way CSOs "see". CSOs, in turn, gather information from within their companies - drawing on activities, stakeholder input, and future scenarios - and translate this assessments, often alongside or against the interpretations of CFOs and consultants, who ultimately give it a stamp of approval. This process of constructing devices for gathering and visualizing information, and for displacing knowledge from its local contexts into standardized inscriptions, mirrors how La Pérouse displaced geographic knowledge during his travels back to France. In both cases, inscriptions are not passive records - they are active tools for rendering complex realities legible across distance, organizing action, and asserting control. In the case of the CSRD, this exists within a broader project of harmonization.

Furthering these parallels, just as La Pérouse's map did not simply reflect an already-known geography but helped create a new way of seeing and claiming land, the sustainability disclosures under the CSRD do not simply report on a pre-existing "sustainability." Instead, they help shape what sustainability becomes. Sustainability is made through the practices of mobilization, inscription, and valuation that reporting requires. In this process, valuation devices are introduced to make sure that the final reports line up with the *mission* the CSRD sets. Sustainability gets frames in specific ways: environmental, social, and governance factors are valued based on their potential financial risks, their impact on future cash flows, or their effect on a company's reputation or strategies for managing these risks. Materiality assessments play a central role in this, helping decide which sustainability topics matter - mainly by asking whether they are likely to influence the decisions of those "using" the information. In this way, reporting does not just describe sustainability; but it reshapes sustainability into a practice of ensuring visibility, value, and action.

Chapter 5

Conclusion: The Making of Sustainability Information

In this thesis, I have set out to map the network of the CSRD, to understand it as a mobilizing force, and to explore how the reporting process unfolds in practice. In doing so, I have attempted to trace the reporting process, from the directive and standards themselves, to the companies, and back up again to the final report. Integral to this study has been engagement with two sites shaping this process: the documents of the CSRD, and the processes described by the interviewed CSOs. I have shown how sustainability is not a fixed achievement, but a negotiated practice. By analyzing how things are drawn together in this process, I have demonstrated that it is a network of practices, devices, negotiations, and valuations - all aligned with broader goals of harmonization. These processes are not without their tensions. In summarizing my findings from the analysis, it is useful to first return to the research questions posed at the beginning:

- *How is the CSRD framed as a response to a sustainability problem - and what actors, tools, and processes of valuation are mobilized in bringing it into being?*

and,

- *How is the CSRD translated into the Norwegian real estate sector, and how does it challenge and reshape existing practices and collaborations?*

As my analysis has shown how these processes overlap, I deem it as appropriate to answer these questions together. The CSRD can not be separated from the practices and translations that help implement, and challenge it. To do this, I begin by exploring what the research questions, supplemented by the methodological and theoretical tools and approaches, has taught us about this process of sustainability reporting.

5.1 The Broad Ideas of CSRD: Revisited

I began this thesis by mapping how the CSRD engages in issue modification around the issue of sustainability. Broad ideals such as transparency, accountability, and commensuration were

highlighted, but in drawing this thesis to a close, I wish to revisit them. As Latour points out, broad ideas like imperialism, the pursuit of knowledge, or the capitalist spirit mean close to nothing on their own, unless we also consider the material tools and practices - like Mercator's map projection, marine chronometers, and copperplate engravings - that made them possible in the first place (Latour, 1990, p. 25). In a similar spirit, the ideas of the CSRD do not stand alone, like the instruments of exploration Latour describes, they rely on material tools and practices to become actionable and meaningful. In this conclusion, I return to these key ideas and trace how they are materialized, and transformed, through the mobilizations of the CSRD. I begin with accountability.

One of the core ideas the CSRD builds on is accountability. But as with imperialism or the spirit of capitalism in Latour's example, accountability is not a free-floating ideal; it is made real through the tools and practices that sustain it. Accountability is a flexible concept: it travels well across different settings, but its meaning is shaped and narrowed by the tools that are supposed to enact it. Under the CSRD, accountability is increasingly pursued through audits, spreadsheets, and disclosures - tools that privilege standardization and comparability. This shift moves accountability away from direct engagement with sustainability practices and toward the creation of internal systems, processes, and reports. The meaning of accountability in this context therefore comes to be defined by the tools of accounting and auditing, not through the production of tangible outcomes. This shift becomes interesting when studying it following Power (1999), that auditing is not a technical process, but rather a cultural ritual. That the stamp of approval offered by auditing exists as symbolic reassurance that control exists, even when true oversight may be limited. In line with this, that the appearance of managing risks and harms is more important than substantively addressing them. The accountability from auditing being mostly symbolic can be reflected in the interactions described by CSO8, that the reporting process after getting help from an advisor felt like "cheating," when they were encouraged to adjust "answers after the fact to get the final scores to 'look right'" (CSO8). Under the CSRD, accountability is not just supported by technical tools - it is shaped by them. Instead of being about taking responsibility for real-world actions, accountability increasingly becomes about showing the right numbers in the right spreadsheets. What counts as "being accountable" is less about what companies actually do, and more about how well they can document their actions in ways that match the expectations of auditors and reporting frameworks. In this way, the CSRD does not just enable accountability; it modifies it to being more a kind of administrative performance. Responsibility risks becoming something companies perform, rather than something they practice.

Another broad idea at the heart of the CSRD is transparency. But as Latour reminds us, ideals only gain force when they are materialized through tools and practices. Transparency is not simply achieved by making more information available - it is shaped by how visibility is constructed, by whom, and with what tools. Drawing on Power (1999) again, auditing does not actually depend on full transparency. Paradoxically, it is often the opacity and formality of the audit process - the black-boxing of decisions, assumptions, and classifications - that gives reports their authority. Trust comes to be built not by revealing every detail, but by showing that a recognizable, standardized process has taken place. Under the CSRD, the audit stamp

on a sustainability report works the same way. Even if the underlying data is messy, selective, or heavily filtered through valuation devices, the presence of formal reports, verification and comparability creates the appearance of transparency. In this way, transparency shifts from illuminating real sustainability practices to producing a visible, portable artifact that signals order and reliability. Like La Pérouse's map, sustainability disclosures under the CSRD do not simply reveal what is already there. In this view, transparency does not simply disclose pre-existing realities; it performs order, producing the appearance of clarity and control even as underlying complexities and negotiations are displaced or black-boxed. In doing so, the CSRD risks reinforcing a narrow, financially-driven vision of sustainability, where what matters is less the ability to act in the face of complex of environmental and social realities, and more the ability to produce consistent, auditable figures.

The third broad idea shaping the CSRD is commensuration: the belief that different aspects of sustainability can be made comparable across companies, sectors, and countries (Laurent, 2022). Yet as valuation studies remind us (Espeland & Stevens, 1998), making things comparable always requires simplification - and always introduces politics. At the heart of this commensuration is the act of translation: turning diverse, context-dependent environmental and social realities into standardized metrics, risk scores, and financial indicators. This process enables sustainability to be ranked, benchmarked, and priced alongside other corporate risks and opportunities. However, the fragility of this promise became visible in the experiences of many CSOs I interviewed. Several described how, even among companies operating in the same sector, materiality assessments produced strikingly different results. This inconsistency not only strained the ideal of comparability but also undermined their own confidence in the process. As discussed earlier, the hope of smooth commensuration offered by the CSRD was, in practice, experienced as fractured and fragile. Yet, as Espeland and Sauder (2007, p. 72) observe, comparative systems often appear most objective to those furthest removed from their construction. From this perspective of CSOs, positioned deep within the machinery of valuation, the fractures and compromises are glaring. But for external users - investors, regulators, civil society - the distance from these messy internal processes may help preserve the appearance that these results are indeed objective. From the outside, the sustainability reports may seem like clear, objective representations. Yet in reality, the work of making different companies' practices seem comparable often involves heavy simplifications and compromises. In this way the CSRD risks not creating a more accurate picture of sustainability, but instead producing a version that is cleaner, more orderly, and easier to work with - at the cost of hiding much of the complexity underneath. Together, these ideals - reshaped through tools and practices - frame the terrain on which sustainability reporting now operates.

The CSRD does more than integrate sustainability into financial reporting; it attempts to produce sustainability as something that can be acted upon by filtering it through financialized valuation devices. The European Commission has repeatedly emphasized that addressing climate change requires the involvement of the financial sector, and the CSRD reflects this ambition clearly. By requiring sustainability disclosures to be published alongside financial reports - with cross-references between the two - the directive creates both a material and conceptual entanglement between financial and sustainability domains. Sustainability

information is now expected to meet the same standards and forms of financial data. This transformation aligns closely with Latour's (1990, p.60) insight that the most powerful actors work through the "weakest materials" - tables, graphs, reports - inscriptions that allow complex realities to be stabilized and governed at a distance. Under the CSRD, sustainability must be turned into stable, mobile figures that can circulate across companies, auditors, investors, and regulators. Yet the very mechanisms that enable this circulation - the push for optical consistency and standardized comparability - also strip away local context, nuance, and alternative processes of enacting sustainability. As this analysis now moves toward its conclusion, it is important to step back and emphasize the broader point: the sustainability report is not a passive mirror of reality. It is the final link in a long chain of translations, inscriptions, and simplifications. Building on this, the sustainability report should not be seen as powerful just in and of itself. As Latour (1990, p. 40) suggests, an inscription, in this case a report, is just the "fine edge" - the final visible point of a long process of gathering, translating, and filtering information. Its strength does not come from the inscription alone, but from the work that built it: the chain of decisions, simplifications, and validations that allow messy realities to be condensed into stable figures. Under the CSRD, reports pull together scattered sustainability concerns and present them in standardized, comparable forms. But what looks like a neat summary is the outcome of countless choices about what to include, how to frame it, and what is allowed to count. The report doesn't simply reflect sustainability as it is; it helps create sustainability as something that can be seen, judged, and acted upon.

5.1.1 A New Entanglement

This study helps illuminate the emergence of a new entanglement between sustainability, finance, and accounting. This is an entanglement that extends the field of valuation studies, particularly research on financialization. Because the CSRD is still being introduced and its reporting structures have yet to stabilize, it offers a unique opportunity to study how this entanglement takes shape in practice. While previous research has often examined the relationship between two of these domains, the CSRD brings all three into new configurations. Many familiar features of financialization are present: the use of monetary valuation to render nature and sustainability commensurable (Fourcade, 2011); the rise of financial standards that shape organizational priorities (Chiapello, 2016); and the reframing of climate risk as something that threatens financial systems rather than ecosystems or communities (Engen & Asdal, 2024b). What is new, however, is how these financialized mechanisms are increasingly interwoven with external auditing. In this way, the CSRD does not only encourage future-oriented financial assessments, it also formalizes them through verification routines, disclosure templates, and external audit requirements. For many Chief Sustainability Officers, this has transformed their daily work. Tasks that once involved overseeing building materials or managing construction teams are now replaced by forecasting future risks, evaluating sustainability performance in terms of financial materiality, and assessing the impact of their operations on future cash flows. This shift signals a deeper transformation in what it means to work with sustainability and deserves further empirical and theoretical attention, especially as these configurations and entanglements continue to shift and develop.

5.2 Limitations and Suggestions for Further Research

After completing this study, several reflections emerge regarding its limitations and opportunities for further research. One key limitation was my time. As I briefly noted in the methodology chapter, I initially knew only that I wanted to study a process, ideally one connected to the EU. However, identifying a suitable case proved challenging, and I spent several months exploring alternative directions before encountering the CSRD. Due to this late start, I was not able to fully let my understanding of the directive mature, and I was, additionally, not able to prioritize follow-up interviews - an approach that could have provided additional depth and insight, particularly into how practices may evolve over time. There are several reflections I wish to make on possible limitations and suggestions for further research. As I can now reflect back on this process, it becomes clear that a key limitation was that of time. While time has been a limitation in this study, it is also a key opportunity for future research. This thesis captures a snapshot of CSRD implementation during a period of transition, where reporting practices, expectations, and tools are still changing. A longer-term case study that follows how sustainability reporting settles, or continues to shift, over time could offer valuable insight into how both companies and regulators adapt and learn. One concrete entry point is the continued development of EFRAG's standards, which are still being updated and clarified to support implementation.

Another interesting temporal direction for future research is to take a historical look at how the CSRD developed. The directive builds on earlier initiatives, especially the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), and it has gone through several rounds of revision and debate. A study of this policy development process could help explain how ideas about sustainability reporting have changed over time. There is also a wide range of documents that could be explored - such as the European Commission's impact assessment of the NFRD (European Commission, 2020), or hearing documents and consultations from the creation of the CSRD. This kind of research could give valuable insight into how the current directive came to take the shape it has today.

The final suggestion for future research relates to the choice of informants. This thesis focused on Chief Sustainability Officers (CSOs), since they are often the ones doing the hands-on work of putting the CSRD into practice. But future research could include other key actors - like auditors, data analysts, or people working in finance departments. These groups often help decide what should be reported, and what ends up in the final report. Talking to them could give an even deeper insight into how different types of expertise shape the reporting process, and how sustainability data gets translated to sustainability information. Including more voices would help build a more complete picture of how the CSRD is actually working in practice.

Appendix

A Interview Guide

The interviews were semi-structured and guided by the following themes and questions:

Opening: Introduction, information about the project, confirmation of consent to participate and to record the conversation, and whether they have any questions for me.

Background Questions

- Can you tell me a bit about where you work and what your role is?
- What is your educational or professional background?
- How far along are you in this work?
- What does a typical workday look like for you in relation to this work?

Internal and External Composition

- Does the size and resources of your company affect how you work with the CSRD?
- Is the CSRD work connected to your previous sustainability efforts?
- How have you chosen to organize the work on the reporting?
- Have you, for example, assembled a working group or something similar? Who is involved, and how is responsibility distributed?
- Do you collaborate across departments within the company? What does that collaboration look like in practice?
- How has it been to make the CSRD understandable and feasible for those in the working group?
- Has there been any collaboration outside the company?

Data Collection

- Do you use any systems or software when working with the CSRD?
- How was the data transformed or processed to fit into the reporting template?

- What data sources do you use, and how do you ensure that the data is relevant and reliable?

Double Materiality Analysis and Other Assessment

- Can you explain what a double materiality analysis is?
- How did you go about working on it?
- What did this work mean for you concretely in your everyday job?
- Which ESRS standards did you identify as material?
- What do Impact, Risk, and Opportunity mean, and how do you work with these?
- At what point in the process did you conduct a stakeholder analysis? How? What did it tell you?

Reflections and Wrap-Up

- What do you see as the biggest strengths and challenges in this process?
- Is there anything you'd like to add about how you work with the CSRD?
- Is there anything else you'd like to add about how you work with the CSRD?

B Consent Form Template

The following is the consent form used in all interviews:

Vil du delta i Fra internasjonalt regelverk til lokal praksis: Datainnsamling og standardisering under CSRD- implementering?

Formålet med prosjektet

Du inviteres til å delta i et forskningsprosjekt som utforsker hvordan selskaper implementerer Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). Dette direktivet stiller omfattende krav til datainnsamling og analyse for å belyse alle aspekter av selskapers bærekraftspraksis. Med hundrevis av datapunkter – både kvantitative og kvalitative – må data samles inn fra en rekke ulike kilder for å støtte vurderinger av innvirkning, risiko og muligheter (IRO).

Prosjektet undersøker hvordan denne komplekse prosessen utføres i praksis: Hvordan forsøkes mangfoldige og komplekse realiteter å bli transformert til målbare og forutsigbare data? Studien kartlegger i detalj hvordan selskaper samler inn, standardiserer og analyserer data for å oppfylle kravene i CSRD, med særlig fokus på metodikk og praktiske gjennomføringer i datainnsamlingen.

Studien fokuserer på de praktiske sidene ved implementeringen, særlig hvordan selskaper:

- Samler inn data fra ulike kilder.
- Standardiserer og strukturerer både kvantitative og kvalitative data for å oppfylle kravene.
- Utfører analyser for å sikre samsvar med rapporteringskrav og samtidig bidra til strategisk beslutningstaking.

Prosjektet er en del av en masteroppgave ved Senter for Teknologi, Innovasjon og Kultur (TIK) ved Universitetet i Oslo. Data som samles inn vil kun bli brukt til dette forskningsformålet og vil ikke bli benyttet til undervisning, andre forskningsprosjekter eller lagres for fremtidig bruk.

Hvorfor får du spørsmål om å delta?

Du får denne forespørselen fordi du har en rolle som er sentral i selskapets arbeid med implementeringen av Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). Deltakere er valgt ut basert på deres rolle og ansvar knyttet til datainnsamling, rapportering og bærekraftsarbeid.

Hvem er ansvarlig for forskningsprosjektet?

Universitetet i Oslo (UiO) ved Senter for Teknologi, Innovasjon og Kultur (TIK) er ansvarlig for personopplysningene som behandles i prosjektet. Det er ingen samarbeid med andre institusjoner eller eksterne oppdragsgivere i dette prosjektet.

Det er frivillig å delta

Det er frivillig å delta i prosjektet. Det vil ikke ha noen negative konsekvenser for deg hvis du ikke vil delta eller senere velger å trekke deg.

Hva innebærer det for deg å delta?

- Metoder: Data samles inn gjennom semistrukturerte intervjuer. Intervjuene vil fokusere på dine erfaringer og innsikt knyttet til implementeringen av Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD).
- Omfang: Intervjuene vil vare mellom 30 og 60 minutter.
- Personopplysninger: Det vil samles inn opplysninger om din stillingsbeskrivelse og rolle i selskapets arbeid med CSRD, samt annen informasjon som kan knyttes til din yrkesmessige bakgrunn i denne konteksten. Ingen sensitive personopplysninger samles inn.
- Registrering av opplysninger: Intervjuene vil bli registrert som notater og/eller lydopptak for nøyaktighet i analysen. Alle data lagres elektronisk på en sikret server.
- Supplerende dokumenter: Deltakere vil også ha mulighet til å dele relevante supplerende dokumenter knyttet til selskapets arbeid med CSRD, dersom dette er hensiktsmessig og ønskelig. Dette kan inkludere rapporter, analyser eller andre interne dokumenter som gir ytterligere innsikt i prosessene.

Kort om personvern

Vi vil bare bruke opplysningene om deg til formålene vi har fortalt om i dette skrivet. Vi behandler personopplysningene konfidensielt og i samsvar med personvernregelverket. Du kan lese mer om personvern på neste side.

Med vennlig hilsen

Torjus Solheim Eckerhoff

(Forsker/veileder)

Isabella Thalia Starrfield

(Student)

Utdypende om personvern – hvordan vi oppbevarer og bruker dine opplysninger

Det er kun prosjektansvarlig og masterstudenten som vil ha tilgang til personopplysningene frem til de slettes eller anonymiseres etter avsluttet prosjekt. Svarene dine vil bli anonymisert i den endelige masteroppgaven, noe som betyr at du som deltaker ikke vil kunne bli gjenkjent. Opplysningene vil kun brukes til de formålene som er beskrevet i dette

skrivet og vil bli behandlet konfidensielt og i samsvar med gjeldende personvernregelverk. Datamaterialet fra intervjuene vil bli lagret på en sikker forskningsserver og en kryptert disk.

Hva gir oss rett til å behandle personopplysninger om deg?

Vi behandler opplysninger om deg basert på ditt samtykke.

På oppdrag fra Universitetet i Oslo har personverntjenestene ved Sikt – Kunnskapssektorens tjenesteleverandør vurdert at behandlingen av personopplysninger i dette prosjektet er i samsvar med personvernregelverket.

Dine rettigheter

Så lenge du kan identifiseres i datamaterialet, har du rett til:

- å be om innsyn i hvilke opplysninger vi behandler om deg, og få utlevert en kopi av opplysningene,
- å få rettet opplysninger om deg som er feil eller misvisende,
- å få slettet personopplysninger om deg,
- å sende klage til Datatilsynet om behandlingen av dine personopplysninger.

Vi vil gi deg en begrunnelse hvis vi mener at du ikke kan identifiseres, eller at rettighetene ikke kan utøves.

Hva skjer med personopplysningene dine når forskningsprosjektet avsluttes?

Prosjektet vil etter planen avsluttes 05.05.2025. Opplysningene vil da bli slettet.

Spørsmål

Hvis du har spørsmål eller vil utøve dine rettigheter, ta kontakt med:

- Prosjektansvarlig: Torjus Solheim Eckhoff t.s.eckhoff@tik.uio.no
- Vårt personvernombud: Roger Markgraf-Bye via personvernombud@uio.no

Hvis du har spørsmål knyttet til Sikts vurdering av prosjektet, kan du ta kontakt på e-post: personverntjenester@sikt.no, eller på telefon: 73 98 40 40.

Samtykkeerklæring

Jeg har mottatt og forstått informasjon om prosjektet [sett inn tittel], og har fått anledning til å stille spørsmål. Jeg samtykker til:

- å delta i intervju

Jeg samtykker til at mine opplysninger behandles frem til prosjektet er avsluttet

C Sustainability Topics

Topical ESRS	Sustainability matters covered in topical ESRS		
	Topic	Sub-topic	Sub-sub-topics
ESRS E1	Climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Climate change adaptation — Climate change mitigation — Energy 	
ESRS E2	Pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Pollution of air — Pollution of water — Pollution of soil — Pollution of living organisms and food resources — Substances of concern — Substances of very high concern — Microplastics 	
ESRS E3	Water and marine resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Water — Marine resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Water consumption — Water withdrawals — Water discharges — Water discharges in the oceans — Extraction and use of marine resources
ESRS E4	Biodiversity and ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Direct impact drivers of biodiversity loss 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Climate Change — Land-use change, fresh water-use change and sea-use change — Direct exploitation — Invasive alien species — Pollution — Others
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Impacts on the state of species 	Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Species population size — Species global extinction risk
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Impacts on the extent and condition of ecosystems 	Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Land degradation — Desertification — Soil sealing
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Impacts and dependencies on ecosystem services 	
ESRS E5	Circular economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Resources inflows, including resource use — Resource outflows related to products and services — Waste 	

ESRS S1	Own workforce	Working conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Secure employment — Working time — Adequate wages — Social dialogue — Freedom of association, the existence of works councils and the information, consultation and participation rights of workers — Collective bargaining, including rate of workers covered by collective agreements — Work-life balance — Health and safety
		Equal treatment and opportunities for all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Gender equality and equal pay for work of equal value — Training and skills development — Employment and inclusion of persons with disabilities — Measures against violence and harassment in the workplace — Diversity
		Other work-related rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Child labour — Forced labour — Adequate housing — Privacy
ESRS S2	Workers in the value chain	Working conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Secure employment — Working time — Adequate wages — Social dialogue — Freedom of association, including the existence of work councils — Collective bargaining — Work-life balance — Health and safety
		Equal treatment and opportunities for all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Gender equality and equal pay for work of equal value — Training and skills development — The employment and inclusion of persons with disabilities — Measures against violence and harassment in the workplace — Diversity
		Other work-related rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Child labour — Forced labour — Adequate housing — Water and sanitation — Privacy

ESRS S3	Affected communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Communities' economic, social and cultural rights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Adequate housing —Adequate food —Water and sanitation —Land-related impacts —Security-related impacts
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Communities' civil and political rights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Freedom of expression —Freedom of assembly —Impacts on human rights defenders
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Rights of indigenous peoples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Free, prior and informed consent —Self-determination —Cultural rights
ESRS S4	Consumers and end-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Information-related impacts for consumers and/or end-users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Privacy —Freedom of expression —Access to (quality) information
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Personal safety of consumers and/or end-users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Health and safety —Security of a person —Protection of children
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Social inclusion of consumers and/or end-users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Non-discrimination —Access to products and services —Responsible marketing practices
ESRS G1	Business conduct	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Corporate culture —Protection of whistle-blowers —Animal welfare —Political engagement and lobbying activities —Management of relationships with suppliers including payment practices 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Corruption and bribery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Prevention and detection including training —Incidents

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